

University of Lagos Master's Thesis

Human Rights and their impact on the Rule of Law in Emerging Democracies

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ABSTRACT

Human rights arise from the very nature of man as a social animal. This nature also necessitates that man live in communities rather than in isolation, thus leading to the need for rules that regulates the activities that the existence of man entails.

Without rules man would live in chaos. This is because there would be no limit to the exercise of the individual rights of man. Since civilized existence requires the observance of rights, it is necessary to have rules put in place to regulate these rights and their observances.

This is where democracy becomes important. Democracy provides a platform on which a system of government respectful of human rights can be built. Democracy has the characteristic, object and effect of securing members against oppression and depredation at the hands of its institutions. These institutions without the rule of law have the tendency of exercising arbitrariness in its actions and possibly inactions. It is not enough to rely solely on the presence of elections (whether or not they are freely and fairly conducted) and leaders chosen there from as the only offerings of a democratic government. Effective democratic system must make provision for peaceful articulation of demand and resolution of competing claims, thereby promoting a sense of justice and social unity. The rule of law must be upheld in a democratic society. Without the rule of law, democracy is rendered completely empty and toothless, thus creating a fertile ground for serious human rights violation. It is right therefore to assert therefore that the linkage between democracy, human rights and the rule of law cannot be denied. This assertion is further amplified by the euphoria for the democratization of political institutions, the movement towards constitutional democracy by nations of the world and the growing disdain for unconstitutional attitudes of any nation.

In as much as there is universal applaud for democratization of nations, the ambit or scope of practical democracy in emerging democracies differs. This is because the state more often than not seeks to shield its own form of governance system with the cloak of democracy. The values, principles and normative context of democracy are usually partly or totally distorted

This paper attempts to examine the meaning of human rights in line with the relationship with democracy vis-a-vis the rule of law in emerging democracies with a view of exposing the impact human rights has on the rule of law in emerging democracies.

The first chapter will introduce the topic while the second will attempt an in-depth examination of the human rights, constitutional democracy and the rule of law. This is important as the precise scope of these concepts must be understood in order fully appreciate the topic. In the third chapter focus will be primarily give to human rights and the rule of law in emerging democracies. While it will not be practicable to study all of the world's emerging democracies, emphasis will be mainly on emerging democracies in the African continent a cursory look will also be taken on a few emerging democracies outside Africa. Chapter four will examine the factors that are responsible for reducing the effectiveness of human rights and the

implementation of the rule of law in emerging democracies. The fifth chapter will attempt to proffer a solution. The chapter will also conclude the essay.

I hope that this study will provoke issues and bring about change both of ideas and practice in a way that will truly entrench the rule of law in emerging democracies.

CHAPTER ONE

DEFINITION

Human rights are those inherent privileges or interests recognized and protected by the power of the land which the international community recognizes as belonging to all individual by the very fact of their humanity.¹ They have also been defined as entitlements or as urgent interests that belong to all human beings and deserve protection regardless of status. They are basic moral guarantees that people in all countries and cultures allegedly have simply because they are human. Calling these guarantees “rights” suggests that they attach to particular individuals who can invoke them; that they are of high priority; and that compliance with them is mandatory rather than discretionary. They are "rights and freedoms to which all humans are entitled without which they cannot function as human beings. All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.² According to Professor U. O. Umozurike, without right, no society will exist as *“the existence of society presupposes the existence of certain basic rights”*.³ For Osita Eze, human rights represent demands or claims which individuals or groups make on society, which are either protected by law or are still aspirations to be attained in the future.⁴ They define and affirm humanity, exist to ensure that human life remains sacred and guarantee that humanity and injustice are prevented or redressed.⁵

The contexts, challenges and prospects for human rights all over the world have continued to change considerably in recent years. It would seem that the consciousness of the world has aligned with the desire to improve rights. One important right that appears to have continued to ‘contaminate’ the world is the right to democracy. The world has risen through the era of self determination and undemocratic self-governance structure to the era of democracy. In Africa, for instance, the first trend was liberation struggles led by single - minded nationalists, focused on freeing African peoples from the shackles of colonialism. For Africans, this was a period of great expectations for both national and personal political freedoms.⁶ The democratic model that came with independence showed obvious lack of strong foundations for open, disciplined

¹ C.H. Orji et al. (eds.) **“Juriscope: Know Your Fundamental and Basic Right”**, Vol. 1, 1st Ed. Port Harcourt: Lawquest Ltd. p.1 (2006).

² Article 1, **Universal Declaration of Human Rights** see www.un.org/en/documents/udhr/index.

³ U. O Umozurike, **“Human Rights and Democracy in the 21st Century- The African Challenges”** in M. T. Ladan (ed.) **“Law, Human Rights And the Administration of Justice in Nigeria; - Essays in Honour of Chief Justice M. L. Uwais”** Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press. p. 36. (2001)

⁴ Ibid at p. 38.

⁵ Uchenna Emelonye, **“Nigeria @ 50 - The Rule of Law, Human Rights and Development”**, Nigerian Bar Association Conference Paper. Kaduna. (2010).

⁶ Petrina Amonoo& Abraham Azubuike, **“Point Library: Media, Information, Culture”** Prepared for the World Library and Information Congress: 69th IFLA General Conference and Council Access - 1 - 9 August 2003, Berlin, Germany, p.1. (2003)

and enlightened political discourse and governance. A number of reasons have been adduced for this.⁷

The growth of democratically elected governments and governance has been accompanied by the expansion of legality as more domains of public life are governed by the rule of law established by democratic procedures. This is one of the most appreciated advantages of democracy. Democracy has taken many paths to entrench itself in the polity of most countries. While it has developed fully in most countries, new democracies seem to grapple with a lot of challenges. Democracy in these countries appears to have distorting characteristics. Truly one cannot appreciate democracy without having in its content some core values of human rights. However, this is just one of the major challenges nascent democracies have to deal with. This is especially because there appears to be an alluring force towards authoritarianism by any government that conflicts with the principles of democracy.

The positive correlation between democracy and respect for human rights is based on the assumption that democratic leaders are more accountable to their citizens and that coercive agents within democratic states not only wield less power than other competitive groups, but the availability of less coercive means of conflict regulation (such as elections) provides both a constraining factor and a preferable option. *Respect for human rights and democracy are among the pillars on which our modern societies stand. In the case of human rights they are used as indicators of the peace, security, tolerance, and freedom in a country, and are thus also the prerequisites for the effective sustainable development of a society.*

1.1 INTERNATIONAL CONCERNS FOR HUMAN RIGHTS

International concern for human rights was demonstrated for first time in modern history at the Congress of Vienna held by states that defeated Napoleon in 1815. Freedom of religion was proclaimed, civil and political rights discussed while slave trade was condemned. Conversely, before 1945, individuals were seen mostly as aliens or nationals and were treated as such under the domestic jurisdiction of sovereign states.⁸ The atrocities committed during the First and Second World wars further raised international concern for human rights. With the establishment of the United Nations in 1945, it was realized that human rights cannot be left to domestic jurisdiction. Article 1(3) of the United Nations Charter set out one of the purposes of the UN is to:

"to achieve international cooperation in solving international problems of an economic, social, cultural, or humanitarian character, and in promoting and encouraging respect

⁷ It is believed that the effect of colonialism has not worn off on African as the present leaders appear to govern with autocratic tendencies reflected in colonialism.

⁸ Muhammed T. Ladan, ***“Introduction to International Human Rights and Humanitarian Laws”*** Zaria, Ahmadu Bello University Press. p. 46. (1999).

for human rights and for fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion".

In a global bid to protect human rights, the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) was adopted in 1948. It is intended that the Declaration serve as "*the common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations*".⁹ This Declaration has continued to be a model for international, regional and individual countries throughout the world as most instruments and constitutions reflect the idea behind the Declaration. In fact, it is considered an interpretation of the human rights articles in the UN Charter,¹⁰ which has become something of a constitution for the international community. The catalogue of rights contained in the declaration contain among others dignity of the human person, freedom from torture, cruel, inhuman or also degrading punishment and treatment, right to a fair trial, freedom of conscience and religion, freedom of expression and freedom of association.

The UDHR is a declaration that is not binding on signatory countries, however, its two covenants: The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and its two optional protocols and the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights are binding on state parties that acceded to them. These Covenants together with the UDHR, which are also known as the International Bill of Rights, came into being with the adoption in 1966 of both Covenants. These makes up the basis for many of the more thematic, specific and specialized human rights conventions, treaties and declarations that followed.¹¹ As provided for by the first of these covenants, an 18-member Human Rights Committee was created. In 2006 the Human Rights Council replaced it. It is worthy of note that the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights guarantees a person's right to be involved in political issues such as:

- The right to take part in the conduct of public affairs;
- The right to vote and be voted for;
- The right to assess general in terms of equality the public services of one's country;
- The right to individual or equal decision during elections; and
- The right to equality before the law and equal protection of the law.¹²

Since then numerous other treaties (pieces of legislation) have been offered at the international and regional level. They are generally known as *human rights instruments*. Till date, in the world over, over eighty treaties have been ratified. These instruments seek to protect the rights of all from various angles. For example, to prevent torture, United Nations Convention against Torture (CAT) was adopted 1984 and it entered into force the same year. By ratifying the

⁹ See Preamble to the UDHR.

¹⁰ See Arts. 55 &56.

¹¹ Legal Research and Resource Development Centre "**Human Rights Made Easy**" 3rd ed. Lagos: Florence & Lambard (Nig) Ltd. p.4. (1999)

¹² **Ibid.** pp. 8-13.

Universal Declaration and other instruments, nation states commit themselves to its provisions that must then be reflected in the law and practice of the nation.¹³

While these Instrumental efforts of the United Nations may be adjudged very fragile and incomplete, they provide a ground to put the domestic conduct of the governments under international scrutiny. In addition, the proliferation of these international (and regional) instruments can be seen as an indication of the growing awareness protect all rights whether existing or evolving as the categories of rights seem not closed.

The importance placed on human rights by the international community has led to the establishment of the International Criminal Court by the United Nations General Assembly to try violators of rights in situations of conflict. Violations of human rights happen when one person or group of persons seek to have power and control over an individual or another group of people. In other words, when any state or non-state actor breaches any part of the UDHR, treaty or other international human rights or humanitarian law instruments, violation occurs. They fail to accord respect to their fellow citizens. The Security Council has also established several ad hoc bodies to address perpetrations of human rights violations. The United Nations has in addition established the Human Rights Council which has been placed on the same pedestal with the UN Security Council. These councils are considered below.

International concern of human rights also extends to exerting various kinds of influence on any government that engages in human rights violations with the aim of making such nation change its attitude towards its own citizens. This influence could be friendly or political or even economic and in some cases, military. In extreme cases, confronting brutal dictators, diplomatic, political and economic leverages seem to be ineffective at stopping massive violations of human rights. Thus, the concern that there should be moral limits tends to lead to a quest for an exception to the non-intervention principle that guides international relations.

Intervention is commonly defined as "dictatorial or coercive interference by an outside party or parties, in the sphere of jurisdiction of a sovereign state"¹⁴From an international law perspective; it can be furthermore argued that the non-intervention principle is not an absolute norm in the contemporary international normative system. The UN Charter¹⁵ forbids intervention in matters that are within the domestic jurisdiction of another state. But, first has to be decided which matters fall within the domestic jurisdiction of the state before applying the principle to any case. Violations of human rights principles and values such as the right to democracy are not considered to be one in which is restricted to domestic jurisdiction.

¹³ Jan Ristarp, ***Libraries and the Intellectual Freedom,*** A keynote paper at the conference "Literature to Politics – Politics to Libraries, Copenhagen, 19-11 November, 2000.

¹⁴ H. Bull, ***Introduction' in H. Bull (ed.), Intervention in World Politics,*** Oxford, Clarendon Press, (1984), p. 1.

¹⁵ Article 2 (7).

On a general scale, it seems to be that since the Second World War, international undertakings have transformed the human rights issue from domestic jurisdiction to international jurisdiction. The manner in which any government treats its own citizens is now a matter of legitimate international concern and not simply a domestic issue. Human rights being a matter of international law emphasize that rights do not depend on an individual's nationality. So, its protection cannot be limited to the jurisdiction of any particular state.¹⁶ Therefore, any concern over human rights cannot be refuted as unwarranted intervention. Within the international normative order, one can argue that human rights now constitute the basis on which the international legitimacy of a state is determined. To link international legitimacy to respect of the state for human rights is to link it to domestic legitimacy. That means that international legitimacy is derived from domestic legitimacy and thus, states do not have an autonomous moral standing divorced from their domestic political institutions and processes, respected by the international community.¹⁷ It is widely recognized that the issues of human rights and democratization have found their way into international politics, and become of international concern, a process which has been provided with added impetus in the post-Cold War era.¹⁸ It is now generally accepted that human rights assume priority over national sovereignty. Consequently, States have been compelled to accept international scrutiny of their human rights credentials.¹⁹

Among this wide array of international and regional instruments, the promotion of democracy and human rights through foreign policy-making is particularly important and believed to be an important avenue in the absence of more effective mechanisms to enforce the existing international standards. During the 2001 Cyril Foster Lecture, the erstwhile United Nations Secretary-General, Kofi Annan emphasized international concern in ensuring that democracy is practised by all nation states.²⁰ He stated that while the major concern of the international community in today's world is the restoration of domestic peace, in societies where it has broken down, it cannot be achieved without democratic governance and the realization of human rights. It has also been observed that democracy builds up human relations with each other and thus, affects their internal harmony and development.

It must be noted that over the last decade and more, the United Nations has had to cope with conflicts in which one group's fear of another was cultivated and exploited by political leaders for their own selfish ends. ²¹ A proper appreciation of the tenets of democracy will go a long way to correct these anomalies. Hence, lots of efforts are made to encourage states to observe

¹⁶ Ladan, *op cit.* p. 45.

¹⁷ İhsan Dağı, **"Human Rights, Foreign Policy and the Question of Intervention"**, 6 Journal of International Affairs, p. 3. (2001)

¹⁸ David Forsythe, **"Human Rights in International Relations,"** Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 4-7. (2000).

¹⁹ D. Evans and Rachel Murray, (eds.) **"The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights: The System in Practice 1986- 2000."** Cambridge University Press. p.2.(2002).

²⁰Kofi Annan, *"Why Democracy Is an International Issue"* **Oxford (UK)** Cyril Foster Lecture (2001).

²¹ Ibid.

international human treaties and transform these into their national legislation. These standards provide the normative basis for the strengthening of democracy.

It should be noted that regarding international human rights standards, states have an obligation to protect their populations from the worst atrocities on the basis of international human rights precepts. Also, the inclusion of human rights and democratization concerns in external relations creates political, legal, and moral commitments and dependencies on both sides. Whether one likes it or not, the international actors trying to influence the behaviour of target governments are increasingly pulling deep into domestic politics and becoming one of the actors. On the one hand, this linkage puts limitations on the policies of international actors vis-à-vis the target country: a more 'responsive' and 'accountable' policy, equipped with the right language, the suitable discourse and the relevant instruments is expected from such actor. On the other hand, domestic politics in the target country become dependent on the attitudes of outside actors and render the internal balances fragile.

The first-ever Emerging Democracies Forum which took place in July, 1999 in Yemen brought together political, civic and economic leaders from transitional democracies which eventually produced the Sana'a Declaration. The Declaration reaffirmed developing countries' commitments to democracy and good governance, and urged the international community to renew its commitment to countries working to build democratic institutions and processes and dedicate resources for this task.²²

In April 2000, the Group of 77²³ held the South Summit in Havana, Cuba. At the event, the Group declared its commitment to "a global system based on the rule of law, democracy in decision-making and full respect for the principles of international law and the Charter of the United Nations."

In a Ministerial Conference on "A Community of Democracies" and a non-Governmental conference on "World Forum on Democracy" which took place in Warsaw, Poland in June, 2000, these two events reaffirmed developing and developed countries' commitment to common democratic values and standards. These include the belief that "the will of the people shall be the basis of the authority of Government, as expressed by exercise of the right and civic duties of citizens to choose their representatives through regular, free and fair elections with universal and equal suffrage, open to multiple parties, conducted by secret ballot, monitored by independent electoral authorities, and free of fraud and intimidation."

International concern with human rights is here to stay. This can be seen from the weight of international institutions, the political influence of the most powerful States and the superior mode of legitimating power.

²² Freedom House Press Release. See www.freedomhouse.org.

²³ The largest coalition of developing countries within the United Nations.

1.1.1 United Nations Security Council

The United Nations Security Council has primary responsibility for maintaining international peace and security and is the only body of the UN that can authorize the use of force (including in the context of peace-keeping operations), or override member nations sovereignty by issuing binding Security Council resolutions. It is created by the UN Charter. The UN Charter gives the Security Council the power to:

- Investigate any situation threatening international peace;
- Recommend procedures for peaceful resolution of a dispute;
- Call upon other member nations to completely or partially interrupt economic relations as well as sea, air, postal, and radio communications, or to sever diplomatic relations; and
- Enforce its decisions militarily if necessary.

The Security Council hears reports from all organs of the United Nations, and can take action over any issue which it feels threatens peace and security, including human rights issues. The body has been faced with criticism for failing to take action to prevent human rights abuses, including the Darfur crisis, the Srebrenica massacre and the Rwandan Genocide.

The Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court recognizes the Security Council as having the power to refer cases to the Court, where the Court could not otherwise exercise jurisdiction.

The Council has constantly affirmed its commitment at ensuring that the world peace is attainable. On April 28, 2006, the Security Council adopted resolution 1674 that "Reaffirmed the provisions of paragraphs 138 and 139 of the 2005 World Summit Outcome Document regarding the responsibility to protect populations from genocide, war crimes, ethnic cleansing and crimes against humanity" and committed the Security Council to action to protect civilians in armed conflict.²⁴ These are just a few of the several ways the council undertakes to ensure that rights are protected by states. The presence or entrenchment of the rule of law in any society will also guarantee the protection of these rights.

Before 1991, the focus of the Security Council had mainly concerned situations of military violence; however focus has now moved to include security of persons. Thus, the Council has continued to take part in "peacekeeping operations" under Chapter VI and has also to establish liberal democratic peace, based on civil and political rights. Concern is on essentially national rather than international issues and answers the questions, "Who governs?" and "How humanely?"

²⁴ Security Council passed the landmark resolution, "**World Has Responsibility to Protect People from Genocide**" Oxfam Press Release (2006).

1.1.2. The United Nations Human Rights Council

The United Nations **Human Rights Council** was created in March 15, 2006. The decision to create a new body was born at the 2005 World Summit. The intention was to replace the United Nations Commission on Human Rights,²⁵ with a body that has a mandate to investigate violations of human rights.²⁶ It began its work on June 19, 2006. The Human Rights Council has been a subsidiary body of the General Assembly reporting directly to it. Forty-seven of the one hundred ninety-one member states sit on the Council, elected by simple majority in a secret ballot of the United Nations General Assembly. Members serve a maximum of six years and may have their membership suspended for gross human rights abuses. The Council is based in Geneva, and meets three times a year; with additional meetings to respond to urgent situations.²⁷ The Council was initially created as a subsidiary organ of the General Assembly.

Some of the Council's responsibilities include:²⁸

- to promote universal respect for the protection of all human rights and fundamental freedoms for all, without distinction of any kind and in a fair and equal manner;
- to address situations of violations of human rights, including gross and systematic violations;
- to promote effective coordination and mainstreaming of human rights within the United Nations system;
- to promote human rights education and learning, advisory services, technical assistance, and capacity building;
- to serve as a forum for dialogue on thematic issues on all human rights;
- to make recommendations to the UN General Assembly for the further development of international law in the field of human rights
- to promote the full implementation by UN member states of their human rights obligations and commitments;
- to undertake a universal periodic review of every UN member state's fulfillment of its human rights obligations and commitments; and
- To contribute, through dialogue and cooperation, toward the prevention of human rights violations and respond promptly to human rights emergencies.

²⁵ The Human Rights Commission came into force to implement the provisions of the UN's groundbreaking Universal Declaration on Human Rights. After decades of complaints from Western nations during the Cold War, and from other states targeted by the Human Rights Commission for their behaviour, the commission was scrapped by an overwhelming vote of the General Assembly.

²⁶ UN General Assembly Resolution "60/251 Human Rights Council" (2006)

²⁷ Ball Olivia & Gready Paul, "***The No-Nonsense Guide to Human Rights***" New Internationalist, U.K. p.95. (2007)

²⁸ **Op. Cit.** UN General Assembly Resolution 60/251 .

The Resolution also requires that the Council's work "shall be guided by the principles of universality, impartiality, objectivity and non-selectivity, constructive international dialogue and cooperation with a view to enhance the promotion and protection of all human rights. independent experts (*rapporteurs*) are retained by the Council to investigate alleged human rights abuses and to provide the Council with reports.

The Human Rights Council may request that the Security Council take action when human rights violations occur. This action may be direct actions, may involve sanctions, and the Security Council may also refer cases to the International Criminal Court (ICC) even if the issue being referred is outside the normal jurisdiction of the ICC.²⁹

1.2 DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN RIGHTS PRINCIPLES

Human rights principles provide a vision of a just and peaceful world. Human rights principles are the underlying factor of every one of its instruments. Characterizations of human rights prescribe respect for them in practice, rather than merely as aspirational statements.³⁰Foremost statements of principle of Human Rights as contained in the 1948 United Nations *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (UDHR) identifies human rights as being held by all people equally, universally, and forever. Those rights are interdependent, inalienable and indivisible. interdependence, for example, means that an individual's right to free expression and to participation in government is directly affected by rights to the physical necessities of life, to education, to free association and non-interference by police or other agencies. Inalienability means that those rights are innate: a person cannot lose those rights and cannot be denied a right because it is "less important" or "non-essential." More principles have been developed to add to these three.

The United Nations framework for democracy is based on universal principles, norms and standards. It emphasizes the internationally agreed normative content, drawing on lessons learned from experience; it outlines the areas of support in which the UN has comparative advantage. It, thus, commits the Organization to principled, coherent and consistent action in support of democracy. The influence of the UDHR has been quite substantial. Its principles have been incorporated into the constitutions of most of the more than 185 nations now in the UN. Human rights principles are upheld by the rule of law and strengthened through legitimate claims for duty-bearers to be accountable to international standards.

²⁹ The Security Council referred the human rights situation in Darfur in Sudan to the ICC despite the fact that Sudan has a functioning legal system.

³⁰ This is in spite of the fact that the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is a Declaration. The follow up Covenants - The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and its two optional protocols and the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights - seem to emphasize this.

As statements of principle, national/international human rights codes assume that there will be support for those whose rights are abused or denied, a support that frequently leads to conflicts between governments. As can be rightly expressed, human rights are formulated to promote tolerance, solidarity, peace, and human dignity. All human rights approach must seek to fulfil the attainment of human rights objectives.

An overview of basic human rights principles is considered below.

1.2.1. Universality

The principle of universality of human rights is the cornerstone of international human rights law. This principle, first emphasized in the Universal Declaration on Human Rights in 1948,³¹ has been reiterated in numerous international human rights conventions, declarations, and resolutions. The 1993 Vienna World Conference on Human Rights, for example, noted that it is the duty of States to promote and protect all human rights and fundamental freedoms, regardless of their political, economic and cultural system.

Human rights are the birthright of every single individual. They are the same for everyone, everywhere. No one is exempted, neither man, nor woman, nor child. For critics, the full implications of the universality of human rights appears not to be sufficiently recognized as such recognition would entail a rethinking and revising of a fundamental principle of international relations, i.e., non-interference in the internal affairs of a state. The application of this principle in the field of human rights is the most formidable obstacle to the creation of effective implementation machinery. It will require a major effort of international re-education to extricate human rights from the grip of the principle of non-interference in internal affairs.³²

All States have ratified at least one, and 80% of States have ratified four or more, of the core human rights treaties, reflecting consent of States which creates legal obligations for them and giving concrete expression to universality. Some fundamental human rights norms enjoy universal protection by customary international law across all boundaries and civilizations. These numerous instruments expressly or by implication affirm the universality of human rights. Respect for this principle must, therefore be upheld at all times except where it is absolutely necessary to curtail these rights; such as for safety of persons.

The universality of human rights affords international protection of these rights. The idea behind this conception would suggest that it does not accept derogations on the basis of culture. Cultural relativism would suggest that any international system of protecting human rights would be inappropriate. ³³At the 1993 Bangkok NGO Conference on Human Rights, it was

³¹ Article 1 states that “All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights.”

³² Tore Frängsmyr, & Irwin Abrams,(eds.), “[Nobel Lectures: Peace 1971-1980](#),” World Scientific Publishing Co., Singapore (1997).

³³ Ladan, *op. cit.* p.48.

declared that “universal human rights standards are rooted in every culture”. The Council of Europe also noted in 1991 that human rights, by definition, are universal only because they belong to all being irrespective of where they live or the culture to which they belong.³⁴

While legal protection of human rights at the international level is clearly promoted by the western developed states, it does not mean that the concept of human rights is solely a western concept. Universalists, however, acknowledge that there are exceptions to the general rule, e.g., the voting age may differ from country to country.

1.2.2 Indivisibility

All human rights are indivisible, whether they are civil and political rights or socio- economic. The temptation to oppose civil and political rights, on the one hand, to economic, social and cultural rights, on the other, must be resisted. Both categories are needed. Often, these rights complement one another. When those deprived of their socio-economic rights cannot make their voices heard, they are even less likely to have their needs met. If a person is deprived of one right, his chance of securing the other rights is usually endangered. The right to education and the right of freedom of information and open debate on official policies is necessary to secure full public participation in the process of social and economic development. The freedom of the human mind and the welfare of the human being are inextricably linked. Simply put, there is no hierarchy among rights, and no right can be suppressed in order to promote another right. The African Charter on Human and People’s Rights affirms in its preamble that civil and political rights cannot be disassociated from economic, social and cultural rights in their conception and that the satisfaction of economic and cultural rights is a guarantee for the enjoyment of civil and political rights.

The frequent use of emergency regulations, preventive detention, and draconian law needs to be considered in the light of the indivisibility of human rights rather than in the context of so-called conflicting rights and liberties, or economic development versus political freedom. It is often overlooked that human dignity and the free mind presuppose a whole network of interconnected rights which equally require protection, and the violation of any one of these, by implication, truncates the whole. Attempts are made to justify curtailments of human rights on the ground that a larger national interest is at stake. These are often the first step in a deliberate reduction of the whole network of human rights, when these are perceived as a threat to established interests.

1.2.3 Inalienability

Human rights are inalienable. They should not be taken away, given up, surrendered, or transferred, except in specific situations and according to due process. For example, the right to

³⁴ A. Ibidapo- Obe, “*A Synthesis of African Law*” Lagos: Concept Publications Ltd, p.260 (2006).

liberty may be restricted if a person is found guilty of a crime by a court of law. Consequently, it is imperative to safeguard human rights against violations, abuse, or neglect. This principle also underlies the rights proclaimed by the Universal Declaration on Human Rights (UDHR) which starts by recognising the *“inherent dignity, and the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family”*. The inalienability of human rights was also emphasised in the 1968 Tehran International Conference on Human Rights.³⁵

1.2.4 Interrelated

Human rights concern appears in all spheres of life - home, school, workplace, courts, and markets - everywhere! Human rights violations are interconnected hence it is virtually impossible for human rights violators to be accused of violating only a single right. The improvement of one right facilitates advancement of the others. Likewise, the deprivation of one right adversely affects the others.

1.2.5 Equal and non-discriminatory

Non-discrimination is a cross-cutting principle in international human rights law. The principle is present in all the major human rights treaties and provides the central theme of some of international human rights conventions such as the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women.

The principle applies to everyone in relation to all human rights and freedoms and it prohibits discrimination on the basis of a list of non-exhaustive categories such as sex, race, colour, age and so on. These attributes are those, over which a person has no choice or attributes that, if denied, would result in the infringement of other human rights (such as religion and political ideology). The principle of non-discrimination is complemented by the principle of equality, as stated in Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: *“All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights.”*

1.2.6 Right and Obligation

Human rights entail both rights and obligations. States generally owe human rights to individuals. States assume obligations and duties under international law to respect, to protect and to fulfill human rights. The obligation to respect means that States must refrain from interfering with or curtailing the enjoyment of human rights. For instance, states should refrain from carrying out forced evictions and not arbitrarily restrict the right to vote or the freedom of

³⁵ Proclamation of Tehran, adopted at the International Conference on Human Rights on May 13, 1962, para 2.

association. The obligation to protect requires States to protect individuals and groups against human rights abuses. Thus, States are required to enact laws that create mechanisms to prevent violation of the right by state authorities or by non-state actors. The obligation to fulfill means that States must take positive action to facilitate the enjoyment of basic human rights. This includes taking active steps to put in place institutions and procedures, including the allocation of resources to enable people to enjoy the right. This obligation is sometimes subdivided into obligations to facilitate and to provide for realization. The former refers to the obligation of the state to engage proactively in activities that would strengthen people's ability to meet their own needs – for instance, creating conditions in which the market can supply the healthcare services that they demand. The obligation to provide goes one step further, involving direct provision of services if the right concerned cannot be realized otherwise, for example, to compensate for market failure or to help groups that are unable to provide for themselves.³⁶ At the individual level, while we are entitled our human rights, we should also respect the human rights of others. It is not for governments to select, as suits their own goals, which rights they will respect, protect or fulfill. On the contrary, rights constitute the standard by which governments are to be judged. It is for the purpose of securing rights that governments are instituted; and although governments long established should not be changed for light and transient causes, any form of government that is destructive rather than protective of universal rights may be altered or abolished. Indeed, it is not merely their right, it is their duty, to throw off such governments.

This concept is clearly linked to the States' traditional monopoly on the use of legitimate force to maintain law and order in a democratic society. Consequently, only state agents, and sometimes individuals acting on the instigation of or with the consent or acquiescence of a public official, are said to violate human rights. On the other hand, violent acts committed by private individuals would normally be classified as a common crime and would, therefore, fall under the Criminal Code of any particular country.

1.2.7 Participatory

All people have the right to participate in and access information relating to the decision-making processes that affect their lives and well-being. Rights-based approaches require a high degree of participation by communities, civil society, minorities, women, young people, indigenous peoples and other identified groups.

1.2.8 Accountability and Rule of Law

³⁶ United Nations Development Programme & HURITALK, ***“Human Rights and the Millennium Development Goals: Making the Link”*** Oslo: Oslo Governance Centre and United National Development Programme (Oslo, Norway), p.9. See also: oslogovcentre@undp.org, www.undp.org/oslocentre

States and other duty-bearers are answerable for the observance of human rights. In this regard, they have to comply with the legal norms and standards enshrined in international human rights instruments. Where they fail to do so, aggrieved rights-holders are entitled to institute proceedings for appropriate redress before a competent court or other adjudicator in accordance with the rules and procedures provided by law. Individuals, the media, civil society and the international community play important roles in holding governments accountable for their obligation to uphold human rights. The creation of the International Criminal Court as a permanent court to try human rights violations and atrocities has been commended.

CHAPTER TWO

HUMAN RIGHTS, CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY AND THE RULE OF LAW

Democracy has become a popular concept in every contemporary discourse.³⁷ It is no longer seen in simplistic terms as merely a government of the people by the people for the people. It is seen as a beacon of light and the harbinger of the good things of life. The word which is originally known to have been coined from two Greek words: demos (the people) and Kratos (rule) which simply means people's rule. However, experience has shown that, having gone through the process of the election of representatives to the seat of government, governments have gone on to administer the affairs of state as if democracy had given way to autocracy. While it is now accepted that they may be "variants" of democracy, it remains unacceptable that core elements of democracy be jettisoned as attempt to do so has the tendency to gradually slide a country into autocratic governance. Its importance to democracy is that the citizenry be able to learn whether the government is doing its job properly and acting in the best interests of the people.

According to Rosenfeld, constitutionalism is "a three-faceted concept", as it requires imposing limits on governmental powers, adherence to the rule of law, and the protection of human rights.³⁸ Modern constitutionalism is democratic constitutionalism and modern democracy is a constitutional one. It is easy to ask: Can there be democracy without the rule of law? Can those countries where the rule of law appears to be very weak really be called democracies?

Human rights, constitution entrenched democracies and the rule of law are core elements that cannot be set aside in any democratic government. Democracy does not hang in space. To truly practice democracy, we must appreciate the norms, values and principles of these elements. The extent to which these values are appreciated determines the extent to which democracy can be claimed.

³⁷ A.A. Idowu, "**Human Rights, Democracy and Development: The Nigerian Experience**" 8 Research Journal of International Studies Seychelles p.30. (2008)

³⁸ M. Rosenfeld, (ed.) **Constitutionalism, Identity, Difference, and Legitimacy. Theoretical Perspectives**, Durham & London: Duke University Press, pp. 27-28. (2004).

2.1 CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY/ DEMOCRATIC GOVERNANCE

A constitutional democracy is a veritable principle of power relationship in a rule-ordered society in which case the governed and the government alike derive their rights, power and privileges from the constitution. It embodies a way of life, its distinctive features constituting its claim to moral superiority over other forms of Government; and the fundamental values on which it is grounded, and which it embodies, have in common a devotion to the idea that the individual is the moral centre of the society. It is government by majority rule with protection of minority rights. It is democratic because of its foundations of popular consent and majority rule. It is constitutional because the power of the majority to rule is limited by a supreme law. A constitutional democracy allows coalition and majority rule and is balanced by minority and individual rights, and most rights are balanced by responsibilities. It is also known as liberal democracy.³⁹ It enjoys the mandate from the people, accomplished through free and fair elections, and that guarantees individual freedoms, such as religion, assembly, and speech and the right to live one's own life without excessive government regulation. A liberal democracy may take various constitutional forms: it may be a [federal republic](#), as the [United States](#), [Brazil](#), [India](#) or [Germany](#), or a [constitutional monarchy](#), such as the [United Kingdom](#), [Japan](#), or [Spain](#). It may have a [presidential system](#) (United States, Brazil), a [parliamentary system](#) ([Westminster system](#), UK and [Commonwealth](#) countries), or a hybrid, [semi-presidential system](#) (France). Simply put, a constitutional democracy is a government based on the consent of the people.

Constitutional democracies are guided by a constitution. A constitution is a fundamental system of law of a sovereign state, established or accepted as a guide for governing the state. A constitution fixes the limits and defines the relations of the legislative, judicial, and executive powers of the state, thus setting up the basis for government. It also provides guarantees of certain rights to the people. It could be written (as obtainable in most democracies) or unwritten (as in the United Kingdom). The democratic [constitution](#) defines the democratic character of the state. It must represent the will of the people, and should, therefore, have been arrived at through consensus. Constitutional democracy is the practice of putting democratic governance within constitutional framework for the purpose of preserving their sacrosanctity.

A constitution is often seen as a means of setting limit on the authority of the government. The common justification for these limits is that they are necessary to guarantee the existence of democracy, or the existence of the freedoms themselves. In practice, democracies cannot exist without these specific limits on specific freedoms. For example, allowing free speech for those advocating mass murder undermines the right to life and security. As Kateb aptly frames it, “restriction or limitation on the power of Government is the soul of Constitutional

³⁹ Samuel J. Levine & Russell G. Pearce, ***“Rethinking The Legal Reform Agenda: Will Raising The Standards For Bar Admission Promote Or Undermine Democracy, Human Rights, And Rule Of Law?”*** 77 Fordham Law Review. New York: Fordham University School of Law p.1636 (2009)

Democracy".⁴⁰ It is more correct to say that constitutional democracy cannot take root in any society, without a firm and profound commitment on the part of the political elites to protect the fundamental rights of all.⁴¹

Democracy is not an event. It is a process, which constitutes the creation and maintenance of operational institutions and an appropriate political culture. That culture is nurtured through institutions that embody enhanced opportunities for political participation and competition for all citizens.⁴² It even gives opportunities for non-governmental actors to pressure the Government. Democracy has also been described as the societal institution of government under which a homogeneous people were governed by an electoral process which was open and fair. It was wrapped in the catch phrase, "Government of the people, by the people and for the people".

One of the cornerstones of democracy is that the people must be fully conversant with rights and responsibilities. For a start, the state must be very willing to conscientize the people on what these rights and duties are and put in place certain institutions to monitor its implementation. Indian economist and Nobel Prize laureate, Amartya Sen, spoke about the two perspectives of democracy. One was what he called the "public ballot perspective of democracy". That's reasonably self-explanatory: the ability to hold public elections and to ensure citizens are able to elect the leaders of their choice. The second perspective of democracy is what he called the "public reasoning perspective of democracy". By that he meant the ability of governments to respond to public reasoning,⁴³

The importance of democracy and democratic values was first highlighted in the Charter of the United Nations, as well as in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Article 21 of the Universal Declaration states:

- "(1) Everyone has the right to take part in the government of his country, directly or through freely chosen representatives.
- (2) Everyone has the right to equal access to public service in his country.
- (3) The will of the people shall be the basis of the authority of government; this shall be expressed in periodic and genuine elections which shall be by universal and equal suffrage and shall be held by secret vote or by equivalent free voting procedure."

⁴⁰ See www.anguillaguide.com/article/archive/125

⁴¹ Anwar Ibrahim, "**Universal Values and Muslim Democracy**" 17 *Journal of Democracy* pp.8-9. (2006)

⁴² Amina A. Augie, "**Human Rights and Good Governance in Africa: A Critical Nexus Expanding Human Rights**" Presented at the Fourth African Development Forum (ADF-IV) on the theme "Government for a Progressive Africa" (Addis -Ababa 2004).

⁴³ South African Human Rights Commission "**Human Rights Lecture and Roundtable Discussion on Dignity And Justice For All Of Us: 60th Anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights**" pp.5-6. (Johannesburg, 2007)

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) also contains, inter alia, binding obligations on States Parties in respect of elections, freedom of expression and association and assembly and other vital democratic entitlements.

Since then, democracy has become a theme of a number of international and regional conferences. The rights enshrined in the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and subsequent human rights instruments covering group rights (e.g., indigenous peoples, minorities, people with disabilities) are equally essential for democracy as they ensure an equitable distribution of wealth, and equality and equity in respect of access to civil and political rights. In January, 2007, The African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance (ACDEG) was adopted by the 8th Ordinary Session of the African Union (AU) Assembly, held in Addis Ababa. On 8 November 2007, the General Assembly proclaimed 15 September as the International Day of Democracy.⁴⁴ It was developed as part of the African Union's stated emphasis on promoting democracy and good governance in member states.⁴⁵ The Charter urges member states to take a wide range of measures to promote democracy in member states.

The links between international peace and security, sustainable human development and democratization were all embraced again by the international community with the unanimous adoption of the Millennium Declaration at the Millennium Summit in 2000. The Declaration provides, among others, that no effort will be spared to promote democracy and strengthen the rule of law, as well as respect for all internationally recognized human rights and fundamental freedom together with a resolution to strengthen the capacity of all signatory countries to implement the principles and practices of democracy and respect for human rights, including minority rights."⁴⁶

While democracy means different things to different people as can be seen in the 2005 UN Summit's Outcome Document, there are certain principles that cannot be dispensed with:

*"We reaffirm that democracy is a universal value based on the freely expressed will of people to determine their own political, economic, social and cultural system and their full participation in all aspects of their lives. We also reaffirm that while democracies share common features, there is no single model of democracy, that it does not belong to any country or region, and reaffirm the necessity of due respect for sovereignty and the right of self-determination. We stress that democracy, development and respect for all human rights and fundamental freedoms are interdependent and mutually reinforcing. "*⁴⁷

⁴⁴ See <http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/training13en.pdf>

⁴⁵ Edward R. McMahon, "**The African Charter On Democracy, Elections And Governance: A Positive Step On A Long Path**" Open Society Institute, Africa Governance Monitoring & Advocacy Project Handbook, p.1.

⁴⁶ Section V, paras: 24 and 25.

⁴⁷ Paragraph 135.

This recognition of diversity within the unity of democratic values is also reflected in the Terms of Reference of the UN Democracy Fund.

Democracy may mean many things to many people, but at bottom it rests on two fundamental ideals - the ideal of liberty and the ideal of equality – freedom and equality. This means that democracy must, nevertheless, contain the seeds that will make it recognizable. There are certain minimums which a system of governance must meet before being called a democracy and below which if it drops, it ceases to be a democracy. These ‘minimum standards’ determine whether a democracy is genuine or bogus.

Compulsorily, as earlier discussed, any democracy must be guided by a constitution. It is from this that constitutional democracy derives its root. Without a constitution, any governance system cannot be democratic. It is imperative that constitution has humane provisions with the intention of making it more amenable to the needs of the people.

Democracy must be connected with good governance. Governance is the exercise of political authority and the use of institutional resources to manage society’s problems and affairs. It is a broad concept, encompassing the capacity of the state, the commitment to the public good, the rule of law, the degree of transparency and accountability, the level of popular participation, and the stock of social capital. It is the structure of institutions set in place in an arrangement agreed by the community for the regulation of society’s social stability, for the advancement of the individual human self-fulfillment, and for the realization of the people’s civil, political, social and economic aspirations. It is the agreement of the people, which gives the structure of democratic governance its validity. Governance could be local, national or international. For the purpose of this study, focus shall be on local and national governance. Local governance refers to the institutions, influences, and processes that lead to the authoritative resolution of public decisions at the tier of government closest to the people while national governance is the institution, influences and processes that lead to the authoritative resolution of public decision at the national level. It links the local level. Local governance, more often than not, tends to be a fall out of what is obtainable at the national level.⁴⁸

Democratic governance is governance according to the agreed rules and regulations that satisfy the developmental needs and aspirations of members of a given society.⁴⁹ It can also be understood as the capacity of a society to define and establish policies and resolve their conflicts peacefully within the existing legal order. This is a necessary condition for the rule of law along with the separation of powers and a legal system that ensures the enjoyment of individual freedoms and rights -civil, social, political and cultural. This requires institutions based on the principles of equity, freedom, participation in decision-making, accountability, and promoting

⁴⁸ Timothy D. Sisk, **“Global Networks For Democracy Promotion: Enhancing Local Governance”** Case Study for the UN Vision Project on Global Public Policy Networks See www.du.edu/~tsisk p.15.

⁴⁹ Jan L. Nnyeruka & Nlerum S. Okogbule, **“Sustainable Democratic Governance And The Rule Of Law: Whither Nigeria?”** (2000/2001) Vol. 6 PCLJ (Port Harcourt, Chigaung Law Publishers) p. 142.

the inclusion of the most vulnerable sectors of society. Dr. Salim Ahmed Salim described democratic governance as a political and social economic framework in which every person and community becomes an equal member of society and is provided with a role that contributes in shaping the destiny of society. It incorporates norms, relations, values, procedures institutions, duties and obligations. It is a totality that encompasses the political, social and economic domain in a mutually and reinforcing manner.⁵⁰

In order to access governance of any kind, three aspects are often highlighted. These are the form of the political regime, the processes by which authority is exercised in the management of a country's economic and social resources and the capacity of government to formulate and to implement public policies and to carry out its duties. Democracy is expected to employ democratic means in these core features. This means that the political regime must be democratic; the process by which the government exercises authority must respect rights and exclude arbitrariness. It is also important for governance in a democratic environment to have regard to the needs of the people in its policy formation and implementation.

Furthermore, any democratic governance structure must have a legitimate source of authority. Any authority that derogates from the constitution of a state will not be regarded as legitimate. This is regardless of the fact that it may enjoy the favour of the ruling class. Such governance must be responsive to public expectation, accountable and tolerant of other players. Constitutional democratic governance must also allow for freedom of information.

Democracy is not without its challenges, which are always two-fold, e.g., to ensure majority rule and to respect minority rights, to strengthen communities and to liberate individuals, to empower government and to limit that power at the same time.⁵¹ Making democracy work requires faith, discipline, determination, and creative improvisation.

2.1.1 BASIC ELEMENTS OF DEMOCRACY

At the Universal Declaration on Democracy held in Cairo on the 16th September, 1997, it was declared that democracy must encompass the following features:-

- Democracy is a universally recognized ideal as well as a goal, which is based on common values shared by peoples throughout the world community irrespective of cultural, political, social and economic differences. It is a basic right of citizenship to be exercised under conditions of freedom, equality, transparency and responsibility with due regard for the plurality of views, and in the interest of the polity.

⁵⁰ Salim A. Salim, ***Democratic Governance and the Challenges of Poverty, Peace and Security in Africa***, Lecture delivered in commemoration of the Nigerian Democracy. The Guardian Newspaper, May 30, 2002.

⁵¹ Condoleezza Rice, ***BBC Today-Chatham House lecture*** delivered from Ewood Park, Blackburn, United Kingdom, March 31, 2006. See <http://www.state.gov/secretary/rm/2006/63969.htm>

- As an ideal democracy aims to preserve and promote the dignity and fundamental rights of the individual, to achieve social justice, foster the economic and social development of the community, strengthen the cohesion of society and enhance national tranquility, as well as to create a climate that is favourable for international peace. As a form of government, democracy is the best way of achieving these objectives; it is also the only political system that has the capacity for self-correction.
- Democracy is inseparable from the rights set forth in the international instruments. These rights must, therefore, be applied effectively and their proper exercise must be matched with individual and collective responsibilities.
- Democracy is founded on the primacy of the law and the exercise of human rights. In a democratic State, no one is above the law, and all are equal before the law.⁵²

Further to the above stated and as has been earlier stated, there must be constitutional provisions for any democracy to exist. Constitutional provisions must allow for review from time to time.

A. A. Idowu, analyzing the works of Pericles of Athens and Abraham Lincoln of America, noted that every democracy must have the culture of obedience to laws including lawful orders of our various courts, obedience to the unwritten laws, the conventions of the democratic process and democratic process. There must also be respect for human rights and fundamental freedom. Every democracy must promote and defend human rights. This is especially as modern democracy envisages a new notion conceived in liberty and dedicated to the proposition that all men are created equal. The hallmarks of any democracy would be measured by the extent to which not only governments but also all other stakeholders ensure that human rights and laws are respected and upheld. There must also be an index of good governance and development. All the qualities obviously place the citizens, who constitute the human resources of the nation in a pedestal to love their nation and struggle to contribute to its socio-economic, cultural and political development.⁵³

Another basic element of any democracy is the conduct of elections. Elections that are open, free and fair are *sine qua non* for democracy to exist. Huntington refers to it as the essence of democracy.⁵⁴ According to A. G. A. Bello "... a political system or society cannot be truly called democratic if it is not accompanied by certain conditions, for example, free and fair election in which there is genuine choice of parties and candidates, the rule of law, and respect for human rights or civil liberties."⁵⁵ Free and fairness in this regard entails more than certification by

⁵² *Ibid.*, www.anguillaguide.com/article/archive/125

⁵³ Idowu, *op. cit.* at pp. 30-31.

⁵⁴ Samuel P. Huntington, "**The Third Wave: Democratization In The Twentieth Century**" cited in Makau Mutua, "**Human Rights in Africa: The Limited Promise of Liberalism**", 51 African Studies Review, 21(2008) Electronic copy available at www.ssrn.com

⁵⁵ A. G. A. Bello, "**On the Concepts of Rationality and Communalism in African Scholarship**," in

international monitors.⁵⁶ It further entails that the elections be the culmination of a process, e.g., free and fair procedures of nomination, unfettered debate, and equal access to media and to public spaces that precedes and conditions the actual polling of voters.⁵⁷ Democracy is a means for the people to choose their leaders and these leaders are chosen via elections. The people decide who will represent them in parliament, and who will head the government at the national and local levels. Elections should be periodic in orderly succession to power through popular participation in secret ballot. Those in power cannot extend their terms in office without asking for the consent of the people again in an election. Voters must be able to vote, free of intimidation and violence. Thus, power flows from the people to the leaders of government, who hold power only temporarily. Independent observers must be able to observe the voting and the vote counting to ensure that the process is free of corruption, intimidation, and fraud. There needs to be some impartial and independent tribunal to resolve any disputes about the election results. It must be noted that there exist democratic institutions that practice mono-party system but contrary to the thinking of single-party or military rulers, there is no democracy without political pluralism or multi-partyism.⁵⁸

Good governance is another essential element of democracy. It is frequently used synonymously with democratic governance. A government cannot claim to be democratic unless it is fully accountable to its people and is transparent in the conduct of its business.⁵⁹ The socio-political and human dimension as well as the technical dimension must be put in place in order to produce expected results.⁶⁰

True democracy must have respect for the Rule of Law and equality before the law both in theory and practice. While emphasizing the Rule of Law as the most inseparable aspect of democracy, the International Commission of Jurists, at its Conference in Athens, 1955 expressed the view that the Rule of Law:

“Springs from the rights of the individual developed through history in the age old struggle of mankind for freedom, which rights include freedom of speech, press, worship, assembly

Olusegun Oladipo (ed.), *“The Third Way in African Philosophy”* (Ibadan: Hope Publications Ltd., 2002) p. 247.

⁵⁶ Certification by international monitors that an election was "free and fair" may mean no more than that the registered voters were allowed to vote and their ballots properly counted.

⁵⁷ Thomas M. Franck, **“Democracy, Legitimacy and the Rule of Law: Linkages”** Public Law and Legal Theory Working Paper Series Working Paper 2 (New York University School of Law, 1999) p.5, also in http://papers.ssrn.com/paper.taf?abstract_id=201054

⁵⁸ André Mbata Mangu, **“Constitutional Democracy And Constitutionalism In Africa”**, [Conflict Trends, Issue 2, African Centre for the Constructive Resolution of Disputes \(ACCORD\) , South Africa](#) p.7. (2006).

⁵⁹ This element has been discussed in detail in the earlier part of this chapter.

⁶⁰ The socio-political and human dimension defines the roles, functions, participation of different actors including the way of thinking, behaviour and leadership style of the leaders. The technical dimension refers to the norms, administrative and financial procedures as well as evaluation indicators adopted.

and association and the right to free elections to the end that laws are enacted by the duly elected representatives of the people and afford protection to all"⁶¹

This concept will be looked into in broader extent in the next sub-heading.

Democracy also means being informed and getting involved. It is an umbrella through which citizens are expected to participate individually and collectively in issues that shape their community, nation and world. Citizens have a role to watch carefully how their political leaders and representatives use their powers, and to express their own opinions and interests. Participation can also involve campaigning for a political party or candidate, standing as a candidate for political office, debating public issues, attending community meetings, petitioning the government, and even protesting. A vital form of participation comes through active membership in independent, non-governmental organizations, what we call "civil society. These organizations represent a variety of interests and beliefs participation in civic groups should be voluntary. Political parties are vital organizations in a democracy, and democracy is stronger when citizens become active members of political parties. Democracy depends on citizen participation in all these ways. Participation must, however, be peaceful, respectful of the law and tolerant of the different views of other groups and individuals.

To support the requirement of elections, voting and political parties' participation, it is important that an independent electoral body be set up to oversee these activities. The importance of these elements in a democracy cannot be over-emphasized. Without its existence, true democracy cannot be entrenched. Such electoral body must be independent and is guaranteed by statute or the constitution, autonomous from government and should have a broad mandate based on universal human rights standards. Such democracy protection body⁶² should have adequate powers of investigation and adequate and sufficient resources to carry out its functions.

2.2 THE RULE OF LAW

The rule of law is the cornerstone for all other elements of democracy. It connotes a concept in which the law is autonomous from the government. Together with its preeminent condition, equality before the law, it forms the platform upon which the edifice of democracy rests. It borders on the relationship between state and society and between citizens around an accepted set of political values and rules.⁶³ It protects the rights of citizens, maintains order, and limits the power of government. All citizens are equal under the law. No-one may be discriminated against on the basis of their race, religion, ethnic group, or gender. The rule of law connotes freedom from the exercise of arbitrary power by government and equality before the

⁶¹ Idowu, *op. cit.* at p.33.

⁶² Catherine Musuva, "*Promoting the Effectiveness of Democracy Protection Institutions in Southern Africa - South Africa's Public Protector and Human Rights Commission*", EISA Research Report 41 South Africa, EISA, p. 6. (2009)
See also: www.eisa.org.za

⁶³ Uchenna Emelonye, "*Nigeria @ 50 - The Rule of Law, Human Rights and Development*" Nigerian Bar Association Conference Paper Kaduna, 2010.

law. Where the rule of law is observed, people can have reasonable certainty in advance concerning the rules and standards by which their conduct will be judged, and the requirements they must satisfy to give legal validity to their transactions. Hence for Dicey, the rule of law is contrasted with every system of government based on the exercise by persons in authority of wide, arbitrary, or discretionary powers of constraint, so that no individual could be lawfully punished by the state "except for a distinct breach of law established in the ordinary legal manner before the ordinary courts of the land."⁶⁴

Stephan Klingelhofer and David Robinson described the rule of law to refer to the observed body of international accords and treaties, state constitutions, and written laws which embody the human rights traditions accepted virtually universally (at least in form), and which protect individuals and order society in the respective nations of the world.⁶⁵ This thus goes to show that the rule of law is not only confined to the expressions by which it is captioned by national constitutions.

A. V. Dicey designed three fundamental principles that have become key elements of the rule of law. These elements are supremacy of the law over all, individuals and authorities alike, equality of all before the law and equal amenability of all to the regular law and courts of the land. The third is that the general rules of constitutional law are the result of the ordinary law of the land.⁶⁶ Dicey's exposition was given based on his understanding of the British constitution.⁶⁷

According to Gutto,⁶⁸ key elements of the rule of law, as a living, evolving and dynamic concept are as follows;

1. The making or existence of laws (or agreements), including human rights laws and agreements, that are relevant to the social needs and aspirations of society and that are reasonable and fair to all sectors and groups in society at the national, regional and international levels;
2. Presence of institutions for law enforcement that have the capacity to enforce the laws/agreements and that are independent and impartial at the national, regional and international levels;

⁶⁴ Amichai Magen, *"The Rule of Law and Its Promotion Abroad: Three Problems of Scope,"* 45 Stanford Journal of International Law, p. 51 (2009).

⁶⁵ Stephan Klingelhofer and David Robinson, *"The Rule of Law, Custom, and Civil Society in the South Pacific: An Overview"* 3 www.icnl.org/knowledge/pubs.

⁶⁶ A. V. Dicey, *"An Introduction to the Law and the Constitution"*, 10th ed. London, Macmillan, p.302. (1985)

⁶⁷ Y. M. Yusuf, *"Democracy as a Cornerstone for Good Governance and Rule of Law"* (2002) 5 U. Maid. L.J. 164.

⁶⁸ Shadrack B. O. Gutto, *"The Rule Of Law, Human And Peoples' Rights And Compliance/Non-Compliance With Regional And International Agreements And Standards By African States"* presentation at the African Forum for Envisioning Africa held in Nairobi, Kenya, 26 - 29 April, 2002. pp.6-7.

3. The presence of a critical mass of professionals in the various organs of the institutions for law/agreements enforcement such as the police, the prosecution authorities, the courts, including administrative tribunals and prisons (correctional services) who have the capacity to enforce the laws and who are reasonable, fair, independent and impartial;
4. Reasonable degree of understanding and general commitment in the society as a whole to the principle of governance in accordance with the law and agreement at the national, regional and international levels;
5. The existence of organised and active formations in civil society, especially in the professions and among academics, women, youth, workers, employers (capitalists), peasants, artists, the media, etc, who are conscious and committed to human rights, social justice and the rule of law; and
6. Reasonable degrees of understanding and commitment in society as a whole to the need for continual reform and improvement in the laws/agreements and the enforcement mechanisms at the national, regional and international levels.

The phrase “the rule of law” is seen by many to be of primary importance to transiting and emerging democracies. According to Lord Ashdown, “in hindsight, we should have put the establishment of the rule of law first, for everything else depends on it: a functioning economy, a free and fair political system, the development of civil society, public confidence in the police and the courts.” This view is widely shared many stakeholders and at the same time the idea of rule of law like the concept of human rights and development is subject to multiplicity of interpretations and definitions.⁶⁹ The rule of law is linked to the values of democratic government and human rights guarantees. While democracy is appreciated as the best instrument that humans have devised for ensuring individual liberty, over the long term, this can only be when it exists within a framework of order established by law. Without rule of law, rights remain lifeless paper promises rather than the reality for many throughout the world.

At its most basic the rule of law refers to a State where power is exercised according to, and accountable to, the law.⁷⁰It refers to a system in which law is able to impose meaningful restraints on the state and individual members of the ruling elite, as captured in the rhetorically powerful, if overly simplistic, notions of a government of laws, the supremacy of the law and

⁶⁹ Emelonye, *op. cit.*

⁷⁰ Marise Cremona, “**The European Neighbourhood Policy: Legal and Institutional Issues**”, Center on Democracy, Development, and the Rule of Law Working Paper 24, Stanford Institute for International Studies, <http://cddrl.stanford.edu> 10. (2004)

equality of all before the law⁷¹ In short, the ‘rule of law’ is the principle that no single individual is above the law.⁷² Absence or breakdown of the rule of law is capable of leading to a situation whereby state laws and institutions cannot be relied upon to regulate the behaviour of the government or its citizens.

Further to the elements listed by Gunto⁷³, Corcoran states that for the rule of law to exist in any given society, it must be characterized by certain features. It must have an independent and impartial judiciary. Equality of all must be provided for by law and respected by the institutions. There must exist a functional judicial system through which disputes can be resolved. There must also be due regard and respect for the right to a fair and public trial. A society in which the rule of law is entrenched must have a rational and proportionate approach to punishment and a strong and independent legal profession.⁷⁴ This position was further affirmed by the then Justice of Nigerian Court of Appeal, Oguntade J.C.A., when he said that the rule of law implies that a court must be free to do justice.⁷⁵

Justice Oputa, JSC (as he then was) contributing to the meaning of the rule of law explained thus:

“The Rule of Law presupposes:

- 1. That the state is subject to the law*
- 2. That the judiciary is a necessary agency of the Rule of Law.*
- 3. That Government should respect the right of individual citizens under the rule of law.*
- 4. That the judiciary is assigned by both the rule of law and the Nigerian constitution the determination of actions and proceedings between persons or between government or an authority and any person in Nigeria.”⁷⁶*

The rule of law is meant to safeguard and encourage civil society. It provides a safe space in which people may work and play together, organize, carry out their own activities, and express their own opinions without fear of state intrusion or interference.

The rule of law is thus closely connected to the objective of good governance as a prerequisite for human, political and economic development. The rule of law is a misused, misunderstood, and at times maligned concept. It has been distinguished from the term ‘rule by law’. The “rule by law” is a legal order dependent upon and subject to the government as the power regulator,

⁷¹ Randall Peerenboom, **“Human Rights And Rule Of Law: What’s The Relationship?”**, UCLA Public Law Series, UCLA School of Law, (Los Angeles 2005) 36. See also Georgetown Journal of International Law 19 (2005).

⁷² John Corcoran, **“A New Era for the Rule of Law: Economic Development and Rule of Law”** (Speech given at POLA Conference, Australia 2009) 20090630 Economic Development and Rule of Law.docx (www.lawcouncil.asn.au) p.3.

⁷³ Gunto, **op. cit**

⁷⁴ Gunto **Ibid.**

⁷⁵ *Doma v Ogiri* [1998] 8 NWLR (Pt. 561) 193 at 207.

⁷⁶ *Governor of Lagos State v Ojukwu* [1986] 1 NWLR (Pt 18) 621.

but otherwise containing no substantive moral standards. Rule by law allows a small group of politicians to cover themselves in a cloak of democratic models to continue policies that preserve the corrupt political institutions. Rule by law imposes no brakes or restraint over a government's actions; it can act capriciously, arbitrarily, and unpredictably.⁷⁷ It is also expressed with the term 'rule of men'. In some cases, the "rule of men" is also used to express similar situation. The rule through law amounts to the "rule of men," if the law can be changed unilaterally and arbitrarily, if it is largely ignored, or if the ruler and his or her associates consistently remain above the law.⁷⁸

The concept of the rule of law serves as a theoretical blue print for designing an ideal legal system and establishes equilibrium between power and law. Pure power is arbitrary might while law is a system by which institutions channel power so that it conforms to a people's value and established pattern of expectations. Power and law cannot without the other lead to a stable society. This is because power can become coercive and unpredictable, and law can become inflexible and potentially oppressive. .⁷⁹

The rule of law is not some a magical formula. The rule of law is not a cruise control doctrine whereby law and order are self-regulating. It requires work and constant monitoring and efforts. In totality, the concept presupposes a situation where everything is done according to laid down principles. The promotion of the rule of law must be encouraged as it will not only form an agenda of promoting access to justice and bring the formal system of justice closer to the people but will also ensure that the poorest section of any population, who suffer most from arbitrary implementation are protected.⁸⁰

The rule of law has been established in various stages in the world's democracies. In the first wave of democracy (1826-1926 in Europe and the Americas), the rule of law was, to a large degree, established before serious attempts began to enlarge the franchise. In the second wave, (1946-1965 associated with decolonisation in Asia and Africa), elements of the rule of law were left as part of the colonial inheritance. However, for third wave democracies (since 1974, including S. Europe, Latin America, E. Europe, parts of Asia, and sub-Saharan Africa) there was often only a very limited level of the rule of law in place. These states were faced with having to introduce it after the first competitive elections.⁸¹ This reversal of the historic order of

⁷⁷ Luz E. Nagle, "**On Armed Conflict, Human Rights, and Preserving the Rule of Law in Latin America**" Stetson University College of Law Faculty Research p.11. <http://works.bepress.com>

⁷⁸ Michel Rosenfeld, "**The Rule of Law and the Legitimacy of Constitutional Democracy**" 74 Southern California Law Review 1313 (2001)

⁷⁹ Wiley Y. Daniel, "**The Rule of Law**" Nigerian Law and Practice Journal (Council of Legal Education, Nigerian Law School, 1997), pp.114- 115.

⁸⁰ Bert B Lockwood, Jr. et al (eds.). 22 "**Human Rights Quarterly**" 749. The Johns Hopkins University Press (2002).

⁸¹ Bruce Baker, "**Policing and the Rule of Law in Mozambique**" 13 Policing and Society, 2 (Routledge, UK) 139-158 (2003)

establishing the basic institutions of the modern state before competitive elections are called has been termed 'democratising backwards'.⁸²

2.3 THE NEXUS BETWEEN CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY AND HUMAN RIGHTS

A constitution is not merely a document introduced by the state with the title of 'constitution'. Many authoritarian regimes introduce such documents to justify arbitrary rule. Thailand, for instance, has had a new constitution virtually every time there is a change of power. A genuine constitution makes effort to limit and reverse all forms of arbitrariness. In the same vein, Just as mere constitutions do not make countries constitutional, political parties and elections do not make governments democratic. Several Asian countries have been termed 'illiberal democracies', for while they have periodic elections, they are not governed by the rule of law and do not protect the rights and liberties of their citizens.⁸³ Without genuine democracy, there can be no constitutionalism.

As have been noted, constitutional democracy means more than the functioning of effective representative institutions and an existent constitution. It also means upholding fundamental principles, particularly the rule of law and respect for human rights. Human Rights and the Rule of Law seek to make sense of human rights through the lens of its triumphs and tragedies, its uneven developments and complex demands. Human rights are a subset of the rule of law. The rule is part of democracy in its integrative sense. Respect for human rights is vital for the democratic edifice to stand. A democracy has no *raison d'être* without human rights. Extracting human rights from a democracy would leave it soulless, an empty vessel. Human rights are the jewels in a democracy's crown.

Most democratic countries, constitutions contain elaborate provisions that recognize the existence of rights. While not all human rights are protected, those protected are usually termed 'fundamental'. These 'fundamental' rights are mostly comprised of civil and political rights. In most cases, socio-economic rights are usually neglected and ignored. Where it is not the case, it is not uncommon to 'clausify' them as nonjustifiable. This means that most constitutional democracies may still not be obliged to enforce, promote and protect these 'socio-political' rights. Their constitutional provisions give them a leeway. Thus, constitutional democracy may not be able to promote, protect and fulfill certain rights. This is appalling, albeit an embarrassing situation. Professor Sagay, quoting Julius Nyerere, correctly describes the farmer who scratches a bare living from the soil provided the rains do not fail, his children work at his side without schooling, medical care or even good feeding. Though, he has the freedom to vote and to speak but these are meaningless.⁸⁴ In *Grootboom's case*, the South African court was of the opinion that where a constitution entrenches both civil and political rights and social and

⁸² R. Rose and D. Shin, "**Democratization Backwards: The Problems of Third- Wave Democracies**", 31 British Journal of Political Science, pp 331- 354 (2001).

⁸³ For example, India and Sri Lanka.

⁸⁴ Itse Sagay, "**The Relationship between the Government and the People in a Democracy**" Lecture delivered at the Edo State Public Service Forum, at Oba Akenzua II Cultural Centre, Benin City (2004).

economic rights, the government must make conscious effort to fulfill them. This effort has to go beyond the thought of 'progressive realization'.⁸⁵ This is because human dignity, freedom and equality, are denied those who have no food, clothing or shelter. Affording socio-economic rights to all people, therefore, enables them to enjoy the other rights. This is especially as these rights are interrelated and mutually supporting.⁸⁶ The growing belief that a democracy must actively seek to advance the welfare of its citizens proves this.

To examine the relationship between constitutional democracy and the human rights means also to study, in effect, how well the rule of law and human rights has been applied and respected. It is clear that without the rule of law, constitutional democracy may very well be a mockery of terms without expectation of any salvific function. While it is agreed that some non-democratic states ⁸⁷do, in fact, seem to have had or now have legal systems that meet the requirements of a thin rule of law, it must be emphasized that the success of the rule of law can best be achieved in a democracy and vice-versa. In other words, democracy and rule of law generally tend to be mutually reinforcing. It is pertinent to state that the extent of this 'mutual reinforcement' remains unclear. That means that the characteristics the rule of law must possess to help sustain constitutional democracy and specific role it must assume to ensure a working constitutional democracy is still unclear.

Initial human rights movement paid relatively little attention to the relationship between rule of law and human rights. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights mentions rule of law only in passing in the preamble,⁸⁸ suggesting in typically cryptic fashion that human rights should be protected by the rule of law. Neither the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) nor the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), the other two main pillars of the "international bill of rights," mentions rule of law. Nor do most other early rights treaties, general assembly statements, committee reports or comments appeal to rule of law.⁸⁹ However, with increased recognition and appreciation of human rights, references to rule of law now regularly appear in General Assembly resolutions, committee reports, regional workshop platforms and other human rights instruments. In 2002, the late U.N. Human Rights Commissioner, Sergio Vieira de Mello made rule of law the centerpiece of his brief tenure in office.⁹⁰

Human rights are a necessity for democracy. If human rights are undermined, democracy is also undermined. Both concepts are intertwined. The cardinal principle of equality, of equal human dignity and equal protection, has perhaps been the dominant force or fuel for the

⁸⁵ The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) encourages states to take steps to progressively realize the provisions of the Covenant.

⁸⁶ Per Davis J in *Grootboom v. Oastenberg Municipality and Others* [2000] (3) BCLRR 227.

⁸⁷ It is not uncommon to hear of terms like semi-democracy, pseudo-democracy, illiberal democracy, limited democracy, mandatory democracy ascribed to some states.

⁸⁸ Mary Ann Glendon, "***The Rule of Law in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights***" 2 Nw. U. J. INT'L HUM. RTS. 5 *at para 6.* (2004) Also <http://www.law.northwestern.edu/journals/jihr/v2/5>

⁸⁹ Randall Peerenboom, *op. cit.* p.2.

⁹⁰ *ibid.* p.3

growth of the human rights movement. It, today, informs ideas in many states about indispensable elements of democracy.⁹¹

For genuine democracies, constitutions consist of overarching arrangements that determine the political, legal and social structures by which society is to be governed. Constitutional provisions are, therefore, considered to be paramount or fundamental law. All other laws within a country must abide by and follow the principles of the constitution. If constitutional law itself is inadequate, the nature of democracy and rule of law within a country is affected. This will, in turn, affect citizens' human rights, which can almost only be realized and protected under a rule of law framework. This pertinently describes the relationship that underlies these concepts.

In any democratic society, administration of human rights doctrines is embedded in at least three elements of democracy. These are protection of the fundamental rights, observance of the rule of law and separation of powers of law-making. As a result of these ground rules, enforcement of human rights in a constitutional democracy involves division of labour, for example:

1. The Police are expected only to arrest and investigate an offender;
2. Prosecutors are to lay complaints and evidence against (and in favour) of an offender before a judge;
3. Defence attorneys are to present the defence of a suspect before the court;
4. The courts will be responsible for the interpretation of the law, and to determine the context of the provisions of the law made by the legislature.

Furthermore, major link between democracy and human rights is the availability of mechanism through which those whose rights are violated seek redress and that those who cause the violations are investigated, tried and punished if found guilty or liable. Also, public officials and security operatives who violate people's rights or openly indulge in dehumanization of citizenry should not go unpunished. Human rights serve as moral constraints on political office holders and institutional heads in a democracy.

Constitutionalism is the institutional basis for enforcement of rights in any society. It is safeguarded by the rule of law. Constitutional democracy is safeguarded by the rule of law. Only when the supremacy of the rule of law is established, can supremacy of the constitution exist. Constitutional democracy additionally requires effective laws and their enforcement to provide structure to its framework.

Democracy is based on a proper relationship between the interests of society and human rights. Both society's interests and human rights are part of a unified legal structure that both

⁹¹ Henry J. Steiner, *"Two Sides Of the Same Coin? Democracy and International Human Rights"* 41 ISR. L. REV., 458 (2008)

determine the scope of human rights. This relationship helps understand when the state is justified in restricting human rights. Human rights can only be restrained when it is for a greater public good. This 'good' must be brought to public or societal knowledge by the constitution.⁹²

Notwithstanding their profound influence on society as a whole, Human rights and constitutional democracy could also diverge at some point. Rights, in some manner, fragment, empowering and encouraging people to direct their lives in their separately chosen directions, while democracy tries to draw people into a deeper participation in the society including active engagement in the common enterprise of self-government.⁹³

In the face of their distinct histories, their prominent differences in nature and function, and the deeper institutionalization of rights in international law and institutions, human rights and democracy have become inextricably intertwined. Each, unaccompanied by the other, can realize only part of its potential and survives at its peril. Together, the two complement and fortify each other.

Today human rights and democracy form part of the same grand narrative of aspiration and hope for our sorry world.⁹⁴

⁹² Aharon Barak, ***“Human Rights And Their Limitations: The Role Of Proportionality”***, Annual Lecture in Law And Society in Association With The Law Faculty And Centre For Socio-Legal Studies, University Of Oxford.(2009) See <http://www.fljs.org>.

⁹³ Henry J. Steiner, ***op. cit.*** p. 456 -457.

⁹⁴ ***ibid.*** p. 476.

CHAPTER THREE

HUMAN RIGHTS AND THE RULE OF LAW IN EMERGING DEMOCRACIES

In the preceding chapter of this essay, I have made efforts to explain what human rights and the rule of law means. While the application of the rule of law and human rights seem to be taken for granted especially in countries that practice democracy, it is agreed that the precise scope or meaning accorded to these them could differ. This is especially true in new or emerging democracies where the nation concerned has to learn continually (and unlearn) the true meaning of these terms. By emerging democracies we simply mean those societies that have just opened up for the entrenchment of the principles of democracy. They are societies in which democracy is just gaining ground, where the concept of democracy is just being learned.

Development of the rule of law remains one of the main priorities in nascent democracies and developing nations. The world's conceptions of democracy itself, and its relationship to various freedoms and social and institutional capacities will always be critical. Also the main focus of human rights law has been on the various rights that seek to strengthen, legitimize and entrench liberal democracy.⁹⁵ Most elements of democracy actively help foster the rule of law.

The path to democracy is not, of course, without bumps, with the danger of being compromised, particularly in new democracies. Mostly, any change in the prevailing power structure within a country is viewed by political elites as destabilizing in the short term. Established elites feel that their political (and sometimes economic) status will be lost and they therefore take action to protect position.

3.1. THE RULE OF LAW IN EMERGING DEMOCRACIES

The rise of new democracies in the world over enhanced the notion of the rule of law, strengthened democratic institutions, and promoted constitutional changes. Worthy of note is that the affirmations by power holders of their commitment to advancing the rule of law often do not necessarily translate into real action.

The idea of the rule of law may very well be considered lofty when juxtaposed with the practice in virtually all emerging democracies. Majority of states whose democratic governance are considered nascent are mostly characterized by enduring democracy which if not carefully nurtured may fall back into autocracy. The rule of law is often rightly contrasted with arbitrary power this is because the benefits of a rule of law regime lies in the humanity it brings into governance. Further to the later, any dispensation where arbitrary power reigns are most often found wanting in its practise of the rule of law. In a democracy, authority is supposed to be exercised in the public interest and for the good of society. In developing countries there is a

⁹⁵ Makau Wa Mutua, *"The Ideology of Human Rights"* 36 Va. J. Int'l L. 604 (1995-1996).

general bias that policies formulated cater for the interest of the high and middle class, not the lower class who are thought to be more in need of these policies. The manner of politics practised in these states can be described as misguided.⁹⁶ The *raison d'être* of any government must be the welfare of the people irrespective of their social classes.

A strong rule of law does not necessarily follow from the implementation of political democracy. Only relatively few citizens of emergent democratic countries would say that the apparent global consensus on the importance of the rule of law has translated into actual marked improvement of the state of law in their societies. It involves an all round transparent policies and actions. In developed democratic nations for instance, a President and his deputy as well as state governors and their deputies enjoy immunity only for carrying out those acts that fall within the normal, legitimate duties of their office. When such officials commit crimes, such as Bill Clinton did when he perjured himself in the Monica Lewinsky case, or former Governor Rod Blagojevich of Illinois who tried to auction off Barack Obama's Senate seat, they are arrested, indicted and prosecuted.⁹⁷

Unless these issues bothering the rule of law are addressed democracy will be threaten in these states

3.2. THE RULE OF LAW IN EMERGING DEMOCRACIES IN AFRICA

Over the last two decades there has been a revival of democratic politics in Africa. By 1995, some 38 out of 47 countries in sub-Saharan Africa had conducted elections, many of them for the first time Single-party political systems, which once dominated the African political landscape, are gradually fading away. Legislative and Presidential elections, once episodic and farcical, are becoming a routine and even vigorously contested. This is helping to remake the region's old image as a safe haven for rapacious and politically unaccountable autocrats. Constitutional changes in several African states have brought important new players onto the political scene. The contribution of two regional initiatives, the Africa Union (a new continental political organisation) and the New Partnership for Africa's Development, NEPAD, have had their influence in the importance African states are placing in good governance. NEPAD provides that development is impossible in the absence of true democracy, respect for human rights, peace and good governance. In other words, one can say that NEPAD does not see the possibility of development without the rule of law. Furthermore, most constitutions now provide for term limits for Presidents. It is worthy of note that the constitution despite its

⁹⁶ The Daily Independent Newspaper interview with Justice Samson Uwaifo "***Corruption level in the country is alarming***"

⁹⁷ Okey Ndibe, "***If Jonathan Were Serious...***" Commentary posted on Sahara Reporters on August 1, 2011. www.saharareporters.com Governor Dannel P. Malloy of Connecticut travelled to New Haven, one of the big cities in his state, for an official meeting. He parked his car at a spot where parking was prohibited. By the time he emerged from his meeting, a municipal officer had issued him a ticket. The fact that he's the governor did not impress the officer who issued that ticket. And unless he goes to court and successfully contests the ticket, Mr. Malloy cannot avoid paying it.

existence, has only recently in emergent democratic countries such as Nigeria and the former Soviet Bloc, began to focus on law as mediating deep social divisions⁹⁸

Oppositionists, in most new democracies, on the other hand have not been very nationalistic in its quest for change or a stronger rule of law. As Kwasi [Prempeh](#) opines, their motivation is by the desire to form the government themselves.⁹⁹ In Ghana, the New Patriotic Party (NPP), between 1993 and 2001, as an opposition party strongly opposed the President's authority to appoint mayors and called for them to be chosen by local popular vote instead. However, in 2001 when it became the ruling party, it not only zealously guarded the President's power to make appointments to mayoralties, but even backed the creation of more such offices.¹⁰⁰

Legislatures in most of Africa's new democracies seem not to have emerged from the shadows of executive hegemony to which decades of military or Presidentialist one-party rule have consigned them. Prempeh believes that what is responsible for this factor ranges from path dependency, to legislative abdication, and constitutional design accounts for this state of affairs.¹⁰¹ According to a recent newspaper report, the police in Ghana has increasingly been disregarding the rule of law and have gradually become trigger-happy. About a month or two ago, teachers who were demonstrating when their leadership were having a meeting with the Labour Commission and the Ministry of Education were brutally beaten by the police for exercising a right guaranteed under the constitution for minor allegations.¹⁰² Another area where Ghana seem not to have made remarkable progress is that of access to justice as some sections of the citizenry are routinely denied access to justice because they cannot afford legal representation.

In spite of the fact that Ghana's democracy continues to be lauded by established democracies, its National Assembly in 2001 re-enacted a 1960s-era law that gives the President authority to establish or abolish government ministries or departments without recourse to the legislative approval.¹⁰³ Remarkably, Ghana has witnessed a great change in its democratic regime since 1993. Ghanaians now enjoy unimpeded access to news, editorial opinions, and political commentary from multiple independent sources. After a three decade-old monopoly, the insurgence of private media has brought a different outlook to the rule of law in Ghana. The private media have played a major role in exposing scandal and malfeasance in public office and have generally kept politicians under scrutiny.¹⁰⁴ In its 2010 index¹⁰⁵, Mo Ibrahim

⁹⁸ Samuel Issacharoff, "**Constitutionalizing Democracy in Fractured Societies**" 82 Texas Law Review 1864 (2003- 2004).

⁹⁹ Kwasi H. Prempeh, "**Progress in Africa: Presidents Untamed**" 19 Journal of Democracy 112 (2008)

¹⁰⁰ *Ibid.* at pp 112-113

¹⁰¹ *Ibid.* at p.114

¹⁰² "**People Die As The Police Mock The Rule Of Law**" see www.theheraldghana.com

¹⁰³ Kwasi H. Prempeh, *op. cit.*, p. 115 (2008)

¹⁰⁴ Kwasi H. Prempeh, "**Marbury in Africa: Judicial Review and the Challenge of Constitutionalism in Contemporary Africa**" 80 Tulane Law Review 51 (2006)

¹⁰⁵ The [Ibrahim Index of African Governance](#) is an attempt to statistically monitor African governance levels throughout all the countries of Africa. It is funded and led by Mo Ibrahim

Foundation ranked Ghana 7th out of the 53 African countries which the report covered. This is remarkably high, on specifics, the country was ranked fourth on rule of law. It also ranked first among Sub-Saharan African countries in five of nine dimensions of the rule of law measured by the World Justice Project's Rule of Law Index TM, a new tool designed to measure countries' adherence to the rule of law. The dimensions measured include whether government officials are accountable under the law, and whether legal institutions protect fundamental rights and allow ordinary people access to justice.

One can also say that it is not yet *uhuru* for the rule of law in Africa's giant, Nigeria. J B Daudu, speaking in a recent seminar stated that political actors have continued to place themselves above the law and their fellow men.¹⁰⁶ The country's legislatures rather than focus on its constitutional role of Law making, has continued to approve mammoth salaries and allowances for themselves. The executive arm of government has a greater task to uphold the rule of law because its various agencies impact on the lives of the totality of Nigerians. With the recent spate of bombings and a general outcry of insecurity in the country, the issue of establishing state police needs to be given prompt attention. Adequate training and funding of security services must not also be overlooked. It would seem that the return to democratic rule in 1999 has opened up the citizens' hitherto suppressed ethnic demands.¹⁰⁷ Only recently the government concluded its amnesty program granted to the militants in its Niger Delta region.

Nigeria is the most populous country in sub-Saharan Africa and the second largest economy in the region after South Africa¹⁰⁸, in the absence of a culture of accountability and transparency, what is professed as democracy would only amount to a hollow ritual of periodically rigged elections. Democracy thrives only when those who hold one office or another become aware that the people they represent are watching their every move.

For late legal luminary, Gani Fawehinmi, Rule of law will collapse if it is not made to rule everybody. There should be no law for the rich and another for the poor. No different law for the powerful and another for the weak. Democracy cannot thrive or be sustained on double

Foundation. It is a fairly comprehensive report compiling 84 indicators across four main categories: safety and rule of law, participation and human rights, sustainable economic opportunity, and human development. It is intended to be a tool for citizens and civil society institutions to monitor how well their government is doing and stimulate constructive debate on governance.

¹⁰⁶ J. B. Daudu is the immediate past President of the Nigerian Bar Association. He made this statement at a one-day seminar on the Rule of Law organised by NBA Rule of Law Committee and the Consultative Dialogue on the general elections in Abuja. See Daily Independent Newspaper, March 30, 2011

¹⁰⁷ Duruji Moses Metumara, ***“Democracy and the Challenge of Ethno-Nationalism in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: Interrogating Institutional Mechanics”*** 15 Journal of Peace, Conflict and Development, 1 Pp 93-98(2010)

¹⁰⁸ Michael Bratton and Peter Lewis , ***“ The Durability Of Political Goods? Evidence From Nigeria's New Democracy”*** 48 Afrobarometer Working Papers 7(2005) see www.afrobarometer.org.

standards.¹⁰⁹ In what could be described as respect for democratic governance, the Nigerian Army only recently dismissed one of its personnel, Lance Corporal Ayodeji Sunday who flouted the Bus Rapid Transport (BRT) laws of Lagos State government.¹¹⁰ This was after the said officer had been court marshalled. It is worthy of note that the said BRT Rules continued to be flouted by “high and mighty” officers.

The police in Nigeria are more like the government police or individual police rather than the people's police. The government at the centre controls it and uses it to fight its critics where the need arises. It was recently reported that one Afolabi Ojediran had his head cut from beatings received from the police at the Ikotun Police Division in Lagos. His offence, he claimed was that his wife had refused the overtures of a police officer. Officially, it was reported at the Police station that he assaulted a police officer.¹¹¹ The spate of insecurity continues to increase which further indicates that police as it exists cannot cope with its role. This has further strengthened the call for state police.

The judiciary has not been exempted from the criticism on how the rule of law has been enhanced and practiced in Nigeria. The feud between the nations Chief Justice and the President of the Court of Appeal, which led to the suspension of the President of the Court of Appeal based on the recommendation of the National Judicial Commission¹¹² has been a topical issues. The Nigerian Bar Association has condemned the act claiming that it is *mala fide*, unacceptable, unconstitutional, illegal and damaging to the image of the nation, the credibility of the judiciary, the legal profession and its fledgling democracy. The consequent appointment of Justice Dalhatu Adamu as the Acting President of the Court of Appeal has been viewed as breach of the due process and the Rule of Law.¹¹³ The Nigerian Bar Association is not the only body that has been against this development. The Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) have dragged the Federal Government to the ECOWAS Court of Justice in Abuja to contest the suspension of Justice Salami. SERAP is alleging violation of the internationally recognised human rights to due process of law; to access to justice and judicial independence; to the rule of law and good governance; to a fair hearing, and to an effective remedy in the suspension of Justice Salami, by the Defendant while his case was pending in

¹⁰⁹ **“Now I am Armed to Fight even More”** interview with Newswatch Magazine 34 Newswatch 10, September 10, 2001

¹¹⁰ **“Army Dismisses Personnel for Flouting BRT Laws”** The Guardian Newspapers, June 28, 2011. www.guardianng.com

¹¹¹ Eniola Akinkuotu, **“Policeman brutalised me because my wife refused to date him ...it's a lie – Policeman”** The Punch Newspaper, September 1 , 2011. <http://www.punchng.com>

¹¹² Both court ranks highest and second highest in the country. The President of the Court of Appeal, Justice Ayo Salami has accused the erstwhile Chief Justice of Nigeria, Justice Aloysius Katsina-Alu of using ‘unholy move’ ‘to push’ him out of the Court of Appeal as result of his refusal to compromise in a matter before the court. The National Judicial Commission after investigating the matter, exonerated the Chief Justice and asked Justice Salami to apologise. Justice Salami instead headed to court to contest the NJC’s decision. He was suspended while the suit was still pending in court.

¹¹³ Communiqué Issued At The End Of The 51st Annual General Conference Of The Nigerian Bar Association (NBA) Held At Port Harcourt, Rivers State From August 21 Through 26, 2011

court and violation of the constitutional provision on the removal of the President of the Court of Appeal. It is pertinent to note that the Nigeria constitution provided that the President of the Court of Appeal shall not be removed before his age of retirement except by the President acting on an address supported by two third majority of the senate.¹¹⁴

Effort to consolidate the rule of law in Nigeria has also been challenged by the growing tide of social tension and communal violence. These conflicts do not have a single motive or trigger. They include large-scale riots with a religious or ethnic dimension, local disputes over land or boundaries, violence directed at government or foreign corporations, state-instigated crackdowns on restive communities, clashes among vigilante groups, and conflict among political factions. What Nigeria appears to lack is the ability to make examples out of erring highly placed personalities who constantly violate the government of the day's acclaimed effort to stabilize the rule of law. Most violators are highly placed in the country, who unless they particularly or personally offend the person of the leaders, never gets prosecuted. For example, Independent National Electoral Commission Chairman, Attahiru Jega, at a National Summit on "Free and Fair Elections" on March 2, said INEC had found multiple voter registration in his \$585million register and even hinted that these persons may be prosecuted. Up until today, nothing has further been done in that regard.¹¹⁵

Kenya like most of Africa's democracies has been fraught with painful "democratic" practises which appear to blur its vision for liberal democracy. The country returned to multi-party politics in the early 90s after nearly three decades of single party rule. With the defeat of former President Arap Moi's appointed successor in 2002 by former Finance minister, Mwai Kibaki, effort was made to enhance the practice of the rule of law by cracking down corruption. All these appear to be mere rhetoric especially with the actions taken by the President to remain in power by compromising the country's electoral commission.¹¹⁶ Widespread international pressure that followed led to the signing of a power-sharing agreement called the National Accord and Reconciliation Act, which recognized Kibaki as President and Odinga as prime minister in February 2008.¹¹⁷ With the adoption of its 2010 Constitution, this power sharing arrangement became substituted with full executive powers with the President. The constitution also makes it necessary for all major appointments to be confirmed by the National

¹¹⁴ See § 292(1)(a)(i) 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, As Amended.

¹¹⁵ Sonala Olumhense, "**Mixed Metaphors-(The Transformation Edition)**" Commentary posted on Sahara Reporters" on July 24, 2011. www. <http://saharareporters.com>

¹¹⁶ The Electoral Commission of Kenya abruptly stopped the count. When counting was resumed, Kibaki surged ahead and, within hours of the result, he was sworn in to his second term at a hastily arranged ceremony. Before counting was stopped, half of the 210 constituencies reported that Odinga was in the lead.

¹¹⁷ Tony Leon, "**The State of Liberal Democracy in Africa: Resurgence or Retreat?**" 12 CATO Development Policy Analysis 15 (2010)

Assembly. The President is also stripped of his power to suspend the National Assembly.¹¹⁸ Commendably, the new constitution contains a Bill of Rights provision. In the real sense of every day events in Kenya, little has changed in terms of how the rule of law has affected human rights in Kenya. In May 2011, Human Rights Watch reported the deportation of the human rights investigator Clara Gutteridge for no obvious wrongdoing.¹¹⁹ Earlier in January 2011, the Kenyan police reportedly shot and killed three men without cause.¹²⁰ This is in spite of the fact that the new constitution has prioritised police reform. According to Makau Mutua a university don, at Buffalo Law School, tribal sentiment and the insincerity of reformists has stalled the growth of human rights and the rule of law in Kenya.¹²¹ It would however seem that Kenya is serious in its efforts to reduce and in the long run eliminate corruption in the country. In July, the High Court ruled that it's former Industrialization Minister, Henry Kosgey should face trial for illegally importing cars into the country.¹²²

Zambia became a republic immediately upon attaining independence in October 1964, its democratisation process started in 1990.¹²³ It has had to contend with an inadequate judicial system as it the capacity to deal effectively with the proliferation of litigation and cases, diminishing courtroom space and a critical shortage of judges and magistrates to expeditiously dispense justice.¹²⁴ In addition, Zambian judges and magistrate has oftentimes been accused of favouritism and abuse of office.¹²⁵ In its monthly essay for June 2011, the *Zambian Economist* describes the role of Judges in the past twenty years to be 'anti-poor'.¹²⁶ Its immediate past President Banda, Zambia's fourth President was democratically elected in 2008 have been accused of amongst other things, not allowing the judiciary to be independent. As elections draw near and in a bid to retain his office, Banda allegedly gave out about 3, 400 government

¹¹⁸ Joel D. Barkan & Makau Mutua, ***“Turning the Corner in Kenya: A New Constitution for Nairobi”*** Council of Foreign Relations Bulletin August 2010

¹¹⁹ Human Rights Watch, ***“Kenya: Human Rights Investigator Deported”*** News Report of May 13, 2011. www.hrw.org

¹²⁰ Amnesty International, ***“Kenya: Triple Killing by Police Must Be Investigated”*** Press Release of January 20, 2011.

¹²¹ Makau Mutua, ***“Why Reforms Have Failed In Kenya”*** Daily Nation Newspaper, Tuesday December 29, 2009 18

¹²² <http://www.voanews.com>, July 29, 2011

¹²³ Luis de Brito, ***“A Challenge for Democracy: Low Turnout in Mozambique, Lesotho and Zambia”*** A paper delivered at the Conference on ***“Electoral Processes, Liberation Movements and Democratic Change in Africa”*** Organised by IESE and CMI held in Maputo in April 2010

¹²⁴ www.pamodzi.ie/project_Zambia.php. The delay in the execution of justice has led to overcrowded prisons. Penitentiaries built by imperial Britain to hold a few hundred are now overcrowded with thousands. Lusaka Central Prison, built in the late 1950s for about 300 inmates, is crammed with about 1,800 inmates, many of them untried in a court of law.

¹²⁵ The *Zambian Economist*, ***“A Poverty of Rule of Law”*** <http://www.zambian-economist.com>. Former President Levy Mwanawasa had been strong on his effort to rid the country of corruption and impose a regime that was high on the rule of law. Unlike most African leaders, President Levy Mwanawasa took to prosecute all found wanting irrespective of their close relationship with the government. He even had former President Fred Chiluba tried. On assuming office, President Banda stopped this trial because of the relationship he enjoyed with Ex- President Chiluba

¹²⁶ The *Zambian Economist*, ***“A Poverty of Justice”***, see also ***“A Poverty of Rule of Law”*** <http://www.zambian-economist.com>.

houses to sitting tenants in Copperbelt Province, stronghold of former opposition leader, Michael Sata.¹²⁷ This action overlooks the principle of accountability that the rule of law represents. What is more worrisome is the fact that this action has not been criticized except in some small quarters. The principle of separation of power enshrined in the rule of law which is meant to enable the organs of government watch one another has been mute in this event. Michael Sata who is the current president of the country has promised a recommitment to the rule of law, and fighting poverty and corruption.¹²⁸

As was reported in Freedom House's 2010 Report "the country at crossroads", former President Yoweri Museveni remains the most significant obstacle to the expansion of democracy and rule of law in Uganda.¹²⁹ Museveni had ruled the Ugandan government for ten years before participating in an election. Even with the elections, he has won every single one he took part in. There are indications that there is no independent institution to conduct elections. Freedom House reports that although the higher courts are generally independent, it is the opposite in the lower courts. Uganda is willing to rely on the argument that its constitution and institutions are young and the institutions still inadequately underfunded,¹³⁰ it is proper to state that this excuse, although prevalent in most of the world's new democracy and also very lame. Ugandan government needs to undertake the electoral and administrative reforms that will substantially improve future elections, ensure adequate separation of power and satisfactorily protect the rule of law. The government of the day does not tolerate opposition. Although the constitution provides that no person shall be subjected to any form of torture or cruel, inhumane or degrading treatment or punishment,¹³¹ Dr. Kizza Besigye, an activist was in April 2011, beaten for no known cause.¹³² Dr. Besigye, a onetime physician of President Museveni, had also contested for the President and lost after which he had alleged at the Uganda Human Rights Commission that he was being trailed by persons whose intention was unknown to him. Since then he has been charged by the government of the day for various offences.¹³³ What is appalling to the rule of law is the manner in which the General Court Martial (GCM) took over the matter from the high court and in spite of the bail granted the accused by the High Court, he remained under cuffs and underwent trial by the martial despite of subsequent court decisions.

¹²⁷ Elias Mbao, "**Rupiah Banda Gives Out Houses in Opposition Leader's Backyard**" posted April 17 2011 <http://www.africareview.com/News>

¹²⁸ <http://www.voanews.com/english/news/africa/Zambia-to-Swear-in-New-President>

¹²⁹ <http://www.freedomhouse.org>

¹³⁰ N. Amanywa Mushega, "**The Rule of Law, Where is Uganda Heading?**" Keynote address delivered at the **a dialogue on Democracy, Good Governance and the Rule of Law in Uganda**, organized by Makerere University Convocation in conjunction with the Human Rights and Peace Centre (HURIPEC), Makerere University.

¹³¹ See Article 24 of the Ugandan Constitution.

¹³² <http://www.africandictator.org>

¹³³ These include rape and treason.

GCM, an offshoot of the military had insisted that they cannot be ordered around by the court, meaning that they refuse to abide by court decisions.¹³⁴

Previously known as Zaire, the Democratic Republic of Congo (DR Congo)'s, current President Joseph Kabila was elected after the assassination of his father, Laurent, who had been President of the country before his death. His election had been praised by international monitors. The country had also suffered from dictatorial rule as Former President Mobutu Sese Seko had rule the country from 1965 - 1997 organizing Presidential elections in which he was the only contestant. According to the United Kingdom Foreign and Commonwealth Office 2010 Report on Human Rights and Democracy, the judicial system in the DR Congo remains flawed with a culture of impunity for even the most grievous of crimes.¹³⁵ This alone deeply undermines the rule of law. The country still grapples with corruption and lack of finances that in effect cripples a number of its institutional activities, for instance, the National Police Force is poorly resourced, undertrained and ill equipped.¹³⁶ In addition, the prison system also suffers as overcrowding makes it difficult to ensure that proper sentences are enforced. Equally appalling is the fact that prison official accept bribes to reduce sentence of criminals.¹³⁷ Freedom of expression is also a casualty as journalists continue to face harassments, threats and violence from the state and local authorities. In April 2010, a journalist Patience Bankome was murdered by men in uniform at his house in Beni, North Kivu. He was the fourth journalist to be killed in recent years, and the case drew the attention of the international community.¹³⁸ President Kabila also condemned the incident. This led to two soldiers being convicted for the killing. In June same year, another activist, Floribert Chebeya Bahizire was killed after meeting with the Police on invitation. Although a senior police officer has been convicted for his murder, there is still a lot to be done in terms of running a government where the rule of law has a place.¹³⁹ In its 2010 Report, Bertelsmann Transformation Index categorically states that there is no rule of law in DR Congo aside from its 2006 election that was generally acclaimed to be free and fair.¹⁴⁰ It has been stated elsewhere in this work that periodic elections sorely, however free and fair, do not necessarily make the rule of law alive in any nation. The latter report shows that there is no separation of power as President Kabila still has a monopoly on power and liberties are bounded by the government.

¹³⁴ Ronald Naluwairo ***"The Trials And Tribulations Of Rtd. Col. Dr. Kizza Besigye And 22 Others: A Critical Evaluation Of The Role Of The General Court Martial"*** HURIPPEC Working Paper 1 2-13 (2006) <http://huripec.mak.ac.ug>

¹³⁵ United Kingdom Foreign & Commonwealth Office ***"Human Office Human Rights and Democracy: The 2010 Foreign & Commonwealth Office Report"*** 184- 193 (UK, 2011). There is rampant sexual violence that goes unchecked by appropriate authorities.

¹³⁶ United Kingdom Foreign & Commonwealth Office ***"op. cit."***

¹³⁷Ryan S. Lincoln, ***"Rule Of Law For Whom?: Strengthening the Rule of Law as a Solution to Sexual Violence in the Democratic Republic of the Congo"*** 26 Berkeley Journal Of Gender, Law & Justice 158 (2011)

¹³⁸ United Kingdom Foreign & Commonwealth Office ***"op. cit."***

¹³⁹ [Dave Peterson](#), ***"Floribert's Killer Convicted but DRC Still Awaits Rule of Law"*** Democratic Digest (2008) www.demdigest.net

¹⁴⁰ www.bertelsmann-transformation-index.de

With the degeneration of its political order beginning in 1999 and the resultant fallout—a civil war in 2002, Côte d'Ivoire has known difficult a democratic terrain.¹⁴¹ When current President Alassane Ouattara won the 2010 Presidential election, it took the intervention of the international community to force former President Laurent Gbagbo out of office. Typical of most African democracies one might say, but an action clearly devoid of any respect that should be accorded to the rule of law in any democratic dispensation. Addressing audience at the International Peace Institute's *African Election Series*, Ambassador Youssoufou Bamba of Côte d'Ivoire, described Gbagbo's clinging to power and the violence that has arisen as a real test for democracy.¹⁴²

Togo was for a long time mired in the pretense of multiparty democracy instituted in the early 1990s by its present President Faure's father, former President Eyadema, whose government ruthlessly dominated Togolese politics and maintained power almost persistently since 1967. In the [Ibrahim Index of African Governance](#) 2010 report, Togo together with Angola and Liberia saw the biggest improvement in overall scores between 2004/05 and 2008/09. Togo's ranking improved from 36 to 43.

As has been earlier emphasised, one element that has resurfaced in this present democratic dispensation is that of clinging to power by the authoritarian ruling incumbents or their families albeit how anti-rule of law it is. When Gnassingbe Eyadema of Togo died in 2005, his son simply took over in total disregard of the Constitution and it took enormous pressure and threats by ECOWAS under the leadership of Olusegun Obasanjo and Mamdou Tandja to force him to step down and organise elections. Faure Gnassingbe eventually won the election which marred by fraud and irregularity, much unlike its 2010 counterpart which was also won by him and was said to be free and fair. Even at that both Obasanjo and Tandja found it very difficult to relinquish power at the expiration of their terms at 2007 and 2010 respectively. While Obasanjo was eventually stopped by a 2006 National Assembly's refusal to endorse his third term agenda, it took a coup d'état to force Tandja out of power. Presently, an independent judiciary does not yet exist. The President of Togo's Judges' Professional Association (APMT) complained at the Association's plenary at the end of 2008 that the Togolese people have to suffer from a judicial system of two speeds, one for the poor and another one for those who are able to buy the judges' conscience. The country still has to cope with abuse of public office while corruption remains rampant.¹⁴³ One aspect that seems to be moving progressively upward is that of civil rights.

The situation is no different in other emerging democracies in Africa. Somalia, for instance seems to be synonymous with anarchy. The Transitional Federal Government controls only a small portion of the country. Currently headed by President Sharif Ahmed, the country had gone through turbulent times to establish the rule of law. What is apparent is that there is

¹⁴¹ www.bertelsmann-transformation-index.de

¹⁴² <http://www.ipinst.org>

¹⁴³ <http://www.bertelsmann-transformation-index.de>

hunger in the face of the nation, according to a Voice of America¹⁴⁴ News report; the President had in fact declared in July 2011, that there was famine in his country. Many of Mozambique's democratic institutions are similarly weak, embryonic or absent, thus undermining the applicability of the rule of law.¹⁴⁵

Countries such as South Africa signify great hope for other African's fledgling democracies. It has a very strong Constitution. Mauritius, like South Africa also has an active constitution. The latter ranked first in the 2010 Mo Ibrahim Index of African Governance Report scoring 90.19 in Safety and the rule of law. Botswana ranked third in the report.¹⁴⁶ When the Bushmen were stopped by the government from accessing wells on their ancestral land, they took the matter to the court of the land which ruled in their favour. This is rare in most of Africa's new democracies as matters against the government are automatically in the government's favour. The recently released 2011 Global Peace Index (GPI) ranked Botswana as the most peaceful country in Africa.¹⁴⁷ This may not be surprising as the country has consistently criticized dictatorial rule in Africa. The country has also disassociated itself from the atrocities committed in Darfur under the leadership of President Bashir in spite of the fact that most African leaders clearly took sides with President Bashir against the International Community.

3.3. THE RULE OF LAW IN EMERGING DEMOCRACIES OUTSIDE AFRICA

The collapse of the Communist one-party states produced a dangerous vacuum of political institutions and values. This resulted in the creation or rather emergence of new regimes in these states.

Russia is an example of an emerging democracy wrought with many struggles. While it still has the status of an electoral democracy, it also has very strong antiliberal and semi-autocratic elements.¹⁴⁸ President Medvedev, who continues to make effort to strengthen the rule of law admits that their efforts have not yielded the best results.¹⁴⁹ This is factual as rights continue to be violated and extra-judicial killings is on the increase. Russia lacks independent media, and journalists who express their disagreement with official policies get persecuted and even

¹⁴⁴ An American International Broadcasting station. This news item was reported on July 19, 2011

¹⁴⁵ Jeremy Astill-Brown and Markus Weimer, ***"Mozambique: Balancing Development, Politics and Security"*** Chatam House Publication p.16 2010.

¹⁴⁶ <http://www.moibrahimfoundation.org>

¹⁴⁷ <http://www.botswanaguardian.co.bw>

¹⁴⁸ Christian W. Haerpfer , ***"Democratic Revolution in Post Communist Europe and Post Soviet Eurasia, 1989-2009"*** Paper presented at the APSA Annual Meeting held in Ontario, Canada(2009)

¹⁴⁹ President Medvedev's opening address at the World Economic Forum Annual Meeting held Davos, Switzerland on 26th January 2011

murdered.¹⁵⁰ It would appear that a total reform of the system is what is needed in Russia. The conduct of the second trial of Mikhail Khodorkovsky and Platon Lebedev, which concluded on 30 December 2010, raised serious questions about the application of justice in Russia.¹⁵¹ Corruption is also a widespread practice in the country. Transparency International's 2010 Corruption Perceptions Index ranked Russia 154 out of 178 countries.¹⁵² This is despite the existence of a Presidential Anti-Corruption Council. The NGOs and Human Rights bodies continue to face great intimidation.

The recent 'Tulip Revolution' in Kyrgyzstan helped to keep its governance system in line with democratic ideas and away from the cul-de-sac of an autocratic regime.¹⁵³ This however has failed to solve the fundamental problem of abuse of power that seems to accompany the office of President. Since obtaining independence in 1991, the country, like most new democracies has experimented with a lot of reforms. In June 2010, the country via referendum, adopted a new constitution. This new constitution appears to be ushering in a new era for the country, as it provides for a first-ever parliamentary system that would allow power to be decentralized and shared among different political parties. The country continues to be faced with the challenge of tribal politics.¹⁵⁴

While Kyrgyzstan continues to make effort to consolidate its democracy, analysts and activist have suggest that for democracy to consolidate rule of law and human rights abuses must be addressed.¹⁵⁵ Security forces continue to be accused of being responsible for several human rights violations.¹⁵⁶ Harald Jepsen of Danish Institute for Human Rights while signing a tripartite agreement with the country's ministry of Justice on one part and Ombudsman on the other parts commended the fact that the country had a vibrant civil society.¹⁵⁷

¹⁵⁰ The death in custody of Sergei Magnitsky was widely condemned by the international community.

¹⁵¹ United Kingdom Foreign & Commonwealth Office *op cit.* 256 (UK, 2011)

¹⁵² In 2009 it was 146th. www.reuter.com/article

¹⁵³ Christian W. Haerpfer, "**Democratic revolution in Post Communist Europe and Post Soviet Eurasia, 1989-2009**" *op cit.* the revolution has shifted the power base from the north to the south.

¹⁵⁴ Anthony Bowyer, "**Kyrgyzstan: Dawn of a Democratic Era**" International Foundation for Electoral Systems Briefing Papers, November 23 2010

¹⁵⁵ <http://www.demdigest.net>. Robert I. Rotberg restated this in, "**When Stats Fail: Causes and Consequences**" p. 15 Princeton University Press 2004.

¹⁵⁶ This includes arbitrary arrest, detention and torture. Azimzhan Askarov, a human rights activist is currently serving a life sentence for complicity in ethnic violence in southern Kyrgystan. Human rights advocates insists that the charges were facilitated for political reasons. In june 2011, he received the prestigious Homo Homini award. See <http://www.demdigest.net> Human Rights watch reported in August same year of the torture and death of an ethnic Uzbek, Kholmiraev. Kholmiraev died two days after he was released from police custody. See: www.hrw.org

¹⁵⁷ Brendan Sweeney, "**Human Rights Move Forward in Kyrgyzstan**" www.humanrights.dk

Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan show a minimum support for citizen's freedom and political rights. Both countries started their democratic journey as semi- autocratic regimes checked by weak institutions. This arrangement was to satisfy western powers who demanded nothing short of democratic governance after the fall out of the communist Soviet Union¹⁵⁸ Azerbaijan has been independent since 1991 and has gone through four constitutional amendments. The last, which was in 2009, excludes term limits for the President.¹⁵⁹ Although the civil society is allowed to operate in the country, their operation has been slowed down by difference in values, limited resources, and government's repression of political opportunity structures amongst others. While the constitution provides for judicial independence, the judiciary is largely dependent on the executive. Like Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan got independence from the Soviet Union in 1991 and has had four constitutional changes since then and has no term limit for the office of the President.¹⁶⁰ President Nazarbayev continues to seek unconstitutional means of extending his rule. In 1995, by a referendum, he extended his tenure to 1999. When another proposition to extend his tenure to 2020 was opposed mainly by the international community, the President hastily moved the elections earlier stated for 2012 to April 2011, thereby weakening the campaign strategies of his opponents. Expectedly, President Nazarbayev won the election.¹⁶¹ Kazakhstan does not guarantee freedom of the media and human rights are stifled. In practice, the rule of law does not count in both countries.

Up until the 90s Indonesia was not thought to be capable of democracy mainly because its social classes were either too small or its ethnic loyalties were too strong.¹⁶²

Hugo Chávez came to power decrying Venezuela's endemic corruption, yet his rule has come to be marked by as much or even greater corruption.¹⁶³ As part of his overhaul of Venezuelan society, Chávez nationalized key industries, instituted land reform, established price controls and enacted a new constitution. The constitution offered an extraordinary opportunity for the country to embrace the rule of law and strengthen the protection of human rights. Nonetheless, since 2000, Venezuelan National Assembly has from time to time granted President Chavez the power to rule by decrees. This act can be seen to connote authoritarianism and totally offend the rule of law. Chavez has further restricted non-governmental organizations and the media. Basically the country does not guarantee freedom of expression as the scope of insult laws has been increased and there is restricted public access to official information. Critics of the government are in the danger of being convicted. In July 2011, Álvarez Paz, a former governor of the state of Zulia and member of an opposition political party, was sentenced to two years in

¹⁵⁸ Martha Bill Olcott & Marina Ottaway, **"Challenge of Semi-Authoritarianism"** : Carnegie Paper No. 7 1, 4 – 7 (1999)

¹⁵⁹ Andreas Heinrich, **" The Formal Political System in Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan.:A Background Study"** No. 107 10-11(Forschungsstelle Osteuropa, Bremen 2010)

¹⁶⁰ **Ibid.**, 20- 24

¹⁶¹ Jim Nicho, **"Kazakhstan: Recent Developments and U.S. Interests"** Congressional Research Service Report 2 (2011)

¹⁶² Gerry van Klinken, **"Patronage Democracy in Provincial Indonesia"** www. ssrn.com

¹⁶³ Thomas Carothers, **"The Rule Of Law Temptations"** 33 The Fletcher Forum of World Affairs 52 Medford, USA. 2009

prison for criticizing the Chávez administration on TV under a charge of disseminating false information a crime incorporated in the Venezuelan Criminal Code by Chávez's allies in the National Assembly in 2005.¹⁶⁴ The government of the day has total disregard for the principle of separation of power which is enshrined in its 1999 Constitution. A 2004 legislation which empowers the President to purge the Judiciary at will has further eroded on the independence of the judiciary.

President Chávez has actively and consistently projected himself as a champion of democracy, not only in Venezuela, but throughout Latin America, his professed commitment to this cause is belied by his government's wilful disregard for the institutional guarantees and fundamental rights that make democratic participation possible.¹⁶⁵

Mongolia has been credited to have gone through remarkable democracy-building over the past two decades. In a recent lecture given by Vidar Helgesen, Secretary-General of International IDEA,¹⁶⁶ he commended the country's effort in undertaking the State of Democracy assessment of its democracy which in itself demonstrates its political will to deepen and expand its democracy. He also noted that democracy might not have reached its perfection especially as the country continues to grapple with the challenge of corruption and lack of female representation. Mongolia has further adopted democracy as its ninth goal in the Millennium Development Goal set to be achieved by 2015 thus emphasising its desired to reinforce democracy in the country.

Taiwan had gone through nearly one hundred years of colonial and authoritarian rule before transforming into an emerging democracy in the 1990s. Since then it has held regular elections.¹⁶⁷ According to the Asian Barometer Project Office,¹⁶⁸ citizens in Taiwan register the lowest level of support for democracy among all new East Asian democracies. This is because they do not think that democracy has performed better than the old regime in some key aspect of governance and has lots of distrust for the political leaders and institutions. They see rampant corruption within government at both the national and local levels. In its survey conducted, almost half (47.1%) of Asian Barometer's respondents feel that they are as equally powerless as they were in its pre democracy days registering a very low level of having a sense of political efficacy under the new regime. Their assessment concluded that freedom of speech is much better in its democracy era, crime rate is said to be on the increase, the gap between the

¹⁶⁴ www.hrw.org/en/news/2011

¹⁶⁵ Alisha Holland et. al., ***"A Decade Under Chávez: Political Intolerance and Lost Opportunities for Advancing Human Rights in Venezuela"*** Human Rights Watch Report September 2008 9

¹⁶⁶ Vidar Helgesen, ***"Global Democracy and the Asia-Pacific Perspective"*** at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Mongolia on 7 June 2011

¹⁶⁷ Nuno Garoupa, Veronica Grembi and Shirley Ching-ping Lin, ***"Explaining Constitutional Review In New Democracies: The Case Of Taiwan"*** 20 Pacific Rim Law & Policy Journal 8 (2011)

¹⁶⁸ The Asian Barometer (ABS) is an applied research program on public opinion on political values, democracy, and governance around the Asian region.

rich and poor has widened and economic development in most respondents' view has declined.¹⁶⁹

Kosovo declared independence from Serbia on February 17, 2008. Expectedly, as one of the world's youngest democracies, Kosovo struggles with uneven rule of law and a weak justice system that is failing its citizens. According to Ambassador Christopher Dell, "*Corruption, violence, and abuse go without redress. The vulnerable lack effective recourse, while the powerful manipulate laws and people to retain power and accumulate wealth.*"¹⁷⁰ Police, public prosecutors and courts continue to face political interference and further abuse their office. Although crime rate in the country is relatively low, the judicial system is weak. With this it is difficult for citizens to have their rights enforced or ensure that the state's institutions properly carry out their functions and properly adjudicate on issues that arise between these institutions and the citizens. In 2010 Kosovo has 269 judges officially which can hardly meet the desire of its teeming population and resolve the over 300,000 cases backlog reported by the crises group in 2010.¹⁷¹ The poor respect for the rule of law in Kosovo has helped to undermine the people's trust in not only the judicial system but the political as well. While it is commendable that Kosovo has made significant efforts in preparing new legislations that should help the rule of law, implementation continues to be a problem. What is encouraging is that the rule of law has improved from what it used to be, perhaps, five years ago. The European Union in a bid to improve the rule of law has established the European Union rule of law mission (EULEX).

Ukraine was the last former Soviet republic to ratify a democratic constitution and has been independent since 1991.¹⁷² It has continuously tried to used elections and compromise to build itself as a nation instead of violence. Although more work needs to be done to bring the rule of law and true democracy to Ukraine, especially on the local level, the country has taken many steps towards creating a democratic system. The Orange revolution of 2004 has been contributory to the voting power of its citizens. This revolution was ignited by the fraudulent Presidential run-off election that year. The revolution however has not succeeded in ripping off all counter rule of law practices. According to Nigeria's Guardian Newspaper, which was based on Freedom House's 2010 report, the country has suffered deteriorating levels of press freedom, instances of election fraud and pollicisation of the judiciary.¹⁷³

Ukraine currently has a bill, signed by President Yushchenko prohibiting the Constitutional Court from deciding on the amendments to the Constitution passed as part of the political

¹⁶⁹ Yu-tzung Chang, Yun-Han Chu, Fu Hu, "**How Citizens Evaluate Taiwan's New Democracy**" Asian Barometer Project Office Working Paper Series: No. 18 pp 3-14 (2004)

¹⁷⁰ Christopher Dell is the U. S. Ambassador to the Republic of Kosovo. He made this Statement at the US Embassy in Pristina in 2010

¹⁷¹ International Crisis Group "**The Rule of Law in Independent Kosovo,**" Report N°204, pp 14-16 19 May 2010

¹⁷² Luke Perry, "**Rethinking the Dominance of Elections and Institutions in Analyzing Democratic Transitions**" 111 The New England Journal of Political Science, No 2 218(2009)

¹⁷³ The Guardian Newspaper, January 13, 2011 13

reform, thus limiting the constitutional powers of the judiciary.¹⁷⁴ It is surprising that the President, who had in 2006, formed the National Committee to strengthen democracy and the rule of law in Ukraine, would be involved in actions inimical to promoting and establishing the rule of law in his own country. While judicial independence may not be all there is to the rule of law, there cannot be a system based on the rule of law without judicial independence.

While Indonesia's democracy is also very new,¹⁷⁵ the country has been very active in its democracy advocacy. In 2008, Indonesia established the Bali Democracy Forum to promote dialogue on democracy in Asia.¹⁷⁶ In spite of the above there are indications that the applicability of the rule of law is not as sturdy as the nation would have the world believe. Defamation is criminal and has been used on a number of occasions to punish government critics. In May 2009, Prita Mulyasari, a mother of two small children, was jailed for three weeks for simply writing a private email to friends complaining about the care she had received from doctors at a local hospital. In 2008, a journalist, Bersih Lubis, was convicted of insulting a public official after he wrote an opinion column that criticised the Attorney-General's decision to ban a high school history textbook.¹⁷⁷ In Indonesia, there are still restrictions on religion that can be practised.¹⁷⁸

While the rule and the necessary freedom may apply in most circumstances, what remains is that the rule of law does not apply to every citizen as they are persons who operate outside the confines of the law.

3.4. THE PROMISE OF EMERGING DEMOCRACIES

The central challenge to sustain and maintain the rule of law in new democracies and turn it into a culture and way of life acceptable and workable for the largest majority of our people involves managing internal tendencies, especially security issues and problems that could impinge on the survival of democracy. This is of national importance and requires comprehensive and committed contribution of all groups and interests that make up each emerging democratic nation. Without the rule of law there is no justice. Painfully as at 1997 only two African countries – Botswana and Mauritius had remained continuously democratic for a considerable period of time. Countries in Africa such as Nigeria and Sudan have had major

¹⁷⁴ It violates Article 8 of the Country's Constitution, which guarantees individuals the right to appeal issues of constitutional rights and freedoms, and Article 147, which gives the Constitutional Court jurisdiction over all "issues of conformity of laws" with the Constitution.

¹⁷⁵ Indonesia's transition from authoritarianism to democracy began with Suharto's fall in 1998.

¹⁷⁶ Thomas Carothers and Richard Youngs, ***“Looking For Help Will Rising Democracies Become International Democracy Supporters?”*** Democracy and rule of law Series© 2011 Carnegie Endowment for International Peace 14 (2011)

¹⁷⁷ **Christen Broecker**, ***“Indonesia's Democracy Still On Shaky Ground”*** www.hrw.org/en/news

¹⁷⁸ Islam, Protestantism, Catholicism, Buddhism, Hinduism and Confucianism are the official religion of Indonesia.

interruption in their democracies making every new democratic dispensation a fresh start or better still, in the words of Carlos Santiso “in a gray middle zone”¹⁷⁹

More often than not, new democracies even while possessing all the formal institutions required in any democracy, they still fail to perform optimally and remain at the embryonic stage of democratic growth. Also it would seem that poverty has a thing to do with progress of the rule of law in most country. Most of Africa’s emerging democracies grapple with poverty as well as proper democratic values. This has led to most emerging democracies to develop their financial institutions as well. Thankfully in the past few years, the country has developed new partnerships that is geared towards leading Africa out of Poverty, an example of this is New Partnership for Africa’s Development.

Nascent democracies’ success or failure cannot avoid being judged based on the how well they have dealt with their social and economic problems; they cannot avoid being accessed on how much the rule of law is appreciated. They must as well encourage themselves and states yet to achieve significant heights in the rule of law appreciation to do so. Where values such as freedom, rule of law, due process and peaceful development are shared, such democracies support one another. While it is said that no country is perfect in its rule of law application, world powers such as the United States are hardly accused for violations as the world sees them trying to support democracy and the rule of law in other countries. These actions could also be seen as helping to keep them on their toes and on the lookout for modes in which they can improve the rule of law in their country (ies). The ECOWAS court had, sometime ago held that the Nigerian child has a right to education that cannot be truncated by either corrupt practices or parental poverty.¹⁸⁰ Till date however, Nigeria like most emerging democracies, continue to wait for the day when socio- economic rights will be recognised by their constitutions as justiciable.

In totality it is not all gory details and gloomy future for all new democracies. The Nigerian 2011 elections were adjudged by most observers as free and fair. While movement has not been fast paced, most emerging democracies in the world appears to be moving forward albeit slowly. South Africa has been exemplary in more ways than one; former President Nelson Mandela has all throughout his term succeeded in putting the country’s interest above his own. He successful handed over after an election that was generally free and fair thus setting the trend in the nation’s polity. The South African constitution entrenches both civil and political rights on the one hand, and social and economic rights on the other. Thus enhancing the rule of law and providing a level ground for a sustainable democracy. It is worthy of note that since the adoption of the Declaration on Criteria for Free and Fair Elections in 1994 by the Inter Parliamentary Union Council, the idea that elections must not merely be held but must be credible as well has broadened tremendously. Worthy of note also is the fact that voters are

¹⁷⁹ Larry Diamond, “*Prospects For Democratic Development in Africa*” The Hoover Essays on Public Policy No. 74 1-4 (1997), See also Carlos Santiso, “*International Co-Operation For Democracy And Good Governance: Moving Toward A Second Generation?*” 13 European Journal of Development Research, no.1 155 (June 2001),

¹⁸⁰ *Serap v Federal Government of Nigeria & Universal Basic Education Commission* (ECW/CCJ/APP/0808)

gradually moving ethnic of clientelistic voting pattern. In recent elections that were adjudged free and fair, winning votes were cast based on the candidature that was thought to be of greater benefit to the country. Similarly, there is a greater appreciation of the concept of change in leadership particularly in democracies where term limits are provided for by the constitution. This can be seen from the resistance put up by citizens toward tenure elongation by Presidents.

Political prisoners have on the whole decreased. Also media houses now operate in a freer environment. For fledgling democracies like Nigeria, wanton proscription of media houses have become a thing of the past.

There has also been a greater appreciation of peace in emerging democracies all over the world. This can be seen in the international effort put into reducing or combating wars and conflict and the trial of leaders, both present and past found to be involved in war crimes.

It is worth mentioning that there appears to be little support for the democracy in Madagascar. After the 2006-2007 Presidential and Parliamentary elections, the general expectation had been that Mauritania might enter a new era of stable civilian rule. However, the coup of August 2008 terminated the presidency of Sidi Ould Cheikh Abdellahi ending democracy's short trip.¹⁸¹

Be that as it may, the future of emerging democracies remains dependent on its adherence to the rule of law.

¹⁸¹ www.bertelsmann-transformation-index.de

CHAPTER FOUR

FACTORS UNDERMINING HUMAN RIGHTS IN EMERGING DEMOCRACIES

Democracy has never been popular and sought for as it has been in the last century. There has been increasing international and domestic pressure to open up political systems and governance structures. However, there is a lot of work to be done around the world to build the culture of democracy – the understanding of its rules, possibilities, obligations and limits, the norms of tolerance, civility, participation, and mutual respect.¹⁸² In many parts of the world democracy is fading, eroding or failing, disillusionment about democracy has replaced the optimism that marked the early 1990s as elected governments are riddled with corruption, incompetence and instability.¹⁸³ Emerging democracies are notoriously fragile, especially in Africa and as such fail to protect or promote human rights thus reducing the effectiveness of the rule of law.¹⁸⁴

In several ways, the challenges of new democracies are a reflection of their elites, history and culture. Particular attention must be focused on the need to preserve and consolidate the political, social and economic environments rendering the development of democracy possible. Attention must also be paid to depreciation of the value of the human person and its fundamental rights. It has increasingly come to light that democracy and good governance are not measured solely by regular free and fair elections but also by the extent to which governments are responsive to the needs of the population and properly accountable to their actions. Most emerging democracies continue to hold periodic elections and refuse to grow in their enjoyment of human rights.

Democracy and human rights have no independent existence outside a dense network of activists, practitioners, institutions, bureaucrats, documents, monitoring technologies, normative practices, legal doctrines and styles of activism. Hence, the ease with which global civic activism has been invaded by state institutions and the likes. For Rod Alence, an important insight is that successful development depends on a political and institutional environment that aligns the political incentives facing governments with the requirements of economic growth and improved social welfare.¹⁸⁵ Many of Africa's emerging democracies admittedly retain neo-patrimonial features and though meeting minimum criteria for democracy fall short of liberal democratic ideals. For example, political authority remains centralised, with constitutions entrenching presidential authority, and with elections often producing a single dominant party, as in Nigeria, flanked by weak and fragmented opposition. Meanwhile, political clientelism and

¹⁸² Larry Diamond, **“Universal Democracy?”** Hoover Institution Publication Policy Review No: 119 June 1st 2003 see <http://repositories.cdlib.org/csd/03-05/>

¹⁸³ Carlos Santiso, **“International Co-Operation for Democracy and Good Governance: Moving Toward a Second Generation?”** 13 European Journal of Development Research 156 (2001).

¹⁸⁴ Jonathan L. Marshfield, **“Evaluating South Africa’s Post-Apartheid Democratic Prospects Through The Lens Of Economic Development Theory”** 9 Richmond Journal Of Global Law & Business 433 (2010)

¹⁸⁵ Rod Alence, **“Political Institutions and Developmental Governance in Sub-Saharan Africa”** 42 J. of Modern African Studies 166 (2004)

related forms of corruption persist, with competition driven less by programmatic or ideological differences than by ethnic or regional conflict over the distribution of state patronage. Many new democracies, in practice, are controlled by a single political coalition that blurs the line between state and ruling party and sees government assets as tools for enhancing its political domination.

The most urgent and pervasive obstacle of human rights in emerging democracies is the absence or decay of the rule of law. This, of course, impacts on a country in various ways, especially as the establishment of a rule of law is critical to building, stabilizing and retaining democracy. These obstacles could be political, legal or institutional. It could also be found underlying in the socio-cultural values of any democracy.

In its year 2000 report on Human development, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) listed the following major impediments to the realization of human rights in new or emerging democracies:

- a) *To integrate minorities and address horizontal inequality between ethnic groups or geographic regions. Perhaps the most persistent weakness of majoritarian democracies is discrimination against minorities and worsening of horizontal inequalities.*
- b) *The arbitrary exercise of power. Elected governments frequently lose legitimacy and popular support when they behave in an authoritarian manner. When elite groups act as if they are above the law or when elected representatives arbitrarily remove judges, civil servants and others, faith in democratic institutions weakens.*
- c) *The neglect of the economic dimension of human rights. Many democracies fail to address the economic and social rights of significant groups, typically because this neglect does not hurt the electoral outcomes for those in power.*
- d) *Finally, failing to deal adequately with the legacy of an authoritarian past can lead to the recurrence of violence and the reversal of democratic rule.¹⁸⁶*

UNDP emphasizes that in the above instances minorities are punished,¹⁸⁷ children remain uneducated and hungry. Journalists are intimidated, judges threatened, political opponents tortured and human rights activists eliminated.

In the following parts of this chapter, the factors that discourage the workability or enforcements of human rights in nascent democracies shall be examined under the following aspects: political, legal, institutional and social-cultural.

4.1 POLITICAL FACTORS

¹⁸⁶ **UNDP Human Development Report 2000**, p. 59. See www.hdr.undp.org/en/media/hrd_2000

¹⁸⁷ In Nigeria, Rwanda, Uganda, Indonesia, Bulgaria and many other countries, conflicts have arisen in one form or another from minority oppressions and their perceived counter-attacks.

An important ingredient in all democracies is the political will of the nation's leaders to improve the quality of governance. Political will and power have a significant effect on human rights and the rule of law in any society. At its most resilient, political will involves a broad consensus among ruling elites, across political parties and sectors of government, in favour of democratic and good governance reforms. Where those in power are much more interested in consolidating and retaining their power than in promoting human rights, democracy or the rule of law, they will be interested in promulgating laws and practices that will help them do this, even if these are contrary to rule of law principles. It refers to the demonstrated credible intent of political actors (elected or appointed leaders, civil society watchdogs, stakeholder groups, etc.) to attack perceived causes or affects a weak democratic system. In Cote d'Ivoire, journalist Venance Konan, writing in pambazuka news, expresses this idea as thus: that Côte d'Ivoire's democratic "impasse ... reveals that the interminable delays in setting a date for the elections are due to the machinations of political elites who continue to benefit from the status quo. While various protagonists on the political stage drag their feet, ordinary citizens continue to suffer grinding poverty and the imminent threat of renewed violence."¹⁸⁸

It is most unlikely to democratize successfully in the absence of the political order that only a state can provide. However the state is unlikely to provide a durable order unless it is legitimated by democracy. This goes to acknowledge that there exists an interaction of state structures and democratic procedures to promote state building the rule of law and democratisation. In the same vein, one of the greatest threats to the rule of law in most emerging democracies is rooted in political insecurity. This is because such governments in a bid to their hold on power often have shorter time horizons and are more preoccupied with placating the specific groups most pivotal to their survival.

Consolidation of political power becomes the main preoccupation of political leaders where the political processes that propel them to power are compromised.¹⁸⁹

The issue of power is remains an ever evolving topic for discussion. Newly developed institutions especially hardly have authority and cannot curb the power of political factions. Elections achieve little against such entrenched power. In practice, donors are setting up organizations, not institutions. Donors think in terms of transplanting best practices, not in terms of finding solutions to locally perceived problems. Put more succinctly, it would seem that every factor, internal and external must play its role to bring about result, positive result. If donor agencies can only transplant best practices, it rests on the home institutions to ensure that the platform for these practices to perform to the optimum.

4.2 LEGAL FACTORS

¹⁸⁸ Kofi Akosah Sarpong, "**West Africa's Burdened Democracy**", The Will Online Journal (10th January 2010) www.thewillnigeria.com

¹⁸⁹ Marietu Tenuche, "**Political Succession And Sustainable Development In Emerging Democracies; Lessons From Ghana And Nigeria**" 12 Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa Clarion University of Pennsylvania, Clarion, Pennsylvania 233 (2010)

It does not require enormous reading or deep reflection to understand the importance of judicial institutions for new and emerging democracies. Much as democracy is associated with electoral contestation and universal rights to suffrage, its operation depends substantially on constitutionalism and the rule of law. In fact, in every society there exists, in one or other fashion, the call for more independence of the judicial organ of state. This is because there is a growing recognition and acceptance that in order for people as individuals, communities, organisations and even nations to live in harmony, there ought to be a set of rules and regulations that are agreed upon, accepted and adhered to uniformly and with a fair degree of predictability. Much as judiciaries are central to the development of the rule of law at an abstract level, they also embody mechanisms to deal with these kinds of tangible problems in democratic development. Judiciaries have the potential to serve as a, if not, the key mechanism of horizontal accountability.¹⁹⁰ By virtue of their potential to help check governmental abuses of power and uphold individual rights, they represent key ingredients for democratic consolidation.

The onset of democratic rule in many new democracies brought new significance to judicial institutions. It brought some processes of political transition and court institutions directly into the political arena, as judges were forced to adjudicate disputes between democratic movements and the incumbents they sought to replace. That judiciaries have had highly constructive roles to play in new democracies seems obvious enough. In many new democracies, weak judicial systems are still too susceptible to political influence and lack the commitment and capacity to make rule of law a reality. Whether they can play such roles in promoting accountability, civil rights, and the rule of law more generally is, of course, an entirely different issue.

Judiciaries need to enjoy some level of autonomy to effectively play these roles. They need to operate in an environment that allows them a great level of independence. This is where the challenge exists. Most emerging democracies have always found a way of tampering with this independence thereby hampering with the enforcement of rights.

One of the ways in which the independence of the judiciary can be hampered is by interlocking its functions with that of political actors. This situation arises mostly when the political environment produces the leaders who, in turn appoint the members of the judiciary. In this sense, it is to be expected that there are fundamental relationships between the political actors and those who are assigned by these to execute the responsibility of interpreting the laws independently; judges thus become pawns in political chessboards.¹⁹¹ Sadly, this seems to be the prevalent situation in most emerging democracies. The Judiciary must be seen to preserve electoral independence as it goes far to safeguard constitutional rights. It helps to defend the will of the majority (however enlightened they are) from encroachment by the impassioned

¹⁹⁰ Peter VonDoepp, ***Judicial Politics in New Democracies: Cases from Southern Africa*** (Lynne Rienner Publishers USA 2009), p. 5. see also www.rienner.com

¹⁹¹ Maxwell A. Cameron, ***Threats to Democracy in the Americas***, FOCAL Policy Paper(FPP-00-8) (Canada, Canadian Foundation for the Americas 2000) See also:www.focal.ca

majority. On the other hand, where necessary institutional safeguards are in place, electoral independence may render judges unaccountable to the people, the ultimate source of all legitimate political power. When judges are unaccountable, they can thwart the will of the majority. This is because in certain circumstances the judiciary as the final interpreter of the Constitution can even where an immediate majority believes itself to be acting within constitutional bounds, potentially thwart even the will of the enlightened majority. In this regard, persons appointed as judges must have the requisite training to ensure that democracy is preserved in any nation. In addition there should also be an institutional watchdog for judges and judicial officers. An example of this is the Nigerian Judicial Service Commission. It follows then that appointments and general duties and responsibilities of these institutional 'watchdogs' must be free from outside interference, where their authority is respected and they remain relatively free from gross interference.

The problem is that judiciaries face inherent weaknesses and represent likely targets of manipulation and subversion at the hands of other political actors,¹⁹² moreover, as the human factor, is also there to consider. Since judges and juridical officials remain part of the community with its entire vicissitudes sometimes it becomes hard to be impartial.¹⁹³

Lawyers are also an essential part of the dynamic capacity of the rule of law because they are carriers of the legal human capital, that is, the raw material on which the legal system draws in the process of interpreting, implementing and adapting legality based on statutory rule or otherwise to local and changing conditions. Legal human capital in this context is taken to mean shared knowledge accumulated within the legal profession in the repositories of judges, lawyers, legislators and law professors.¹⁹⁴

The police and public defenders are also to understand that they operate under the same interpretation of laws and practices and that where they malfunction, human rights are compromised. In countries such as Nigeria, where members of the police are allowed to prosecute accused persons, it behoves them to ensure that the rule of law and natural justice are upheld. Corrupt and unprofessional practices by the Nigerian police have severely undermined the integrity of the Nigerian criminal justice system and, by extension, respect for the rule of law. The police subject victims of crimes to incessant demands for money to investigate and

¹⁹² Peter VonDoepp, *op. Cit.* Pp. 1-15

¹⁹³ In Nigeria, there have been allegations of gross misconduct levelled against the Chief Justice of Nigeria (CJN), Justice Aloysius Katsina-Alu and President of the Court of Appeal, Justice Ayo Isa Salami. Hon. President of the Court of Appeal, Justice Ayo Salami in a suit, (now withdrawn), alleging that the Chief Justice of Nigeria, the Justice A. Katsina-Alu (GCON), had, some time ago, at a meeting called at his instance, requested him to either disband the Sokoto State Gubernatorial Election Petition Appeal Tribunal (Appeal Tribunal) or alternatively direct the Appeal Tribunal to enter judgment for one of the parties. This suit was filed following the transfer of the President of the Court of Appeal to the Supreme Court by the Chief Justice of Nigeria. The transfer itself was unprecedented in the history of the country. See www.sunnewsonline.com

¹⁹⁴ Gillian K. Hadfield, *"Don't Forget the Lawyers: The Role of Lawyers in Promoting the Rule of Law in (Emerging) Market Democracies"* USC Law School Conference Paper (2006), p. 3 available at www.bepress.com

move forward the case, leaving victims who refuse or are unable to pay with little hope for justice.

Inadequate capacity of the courts and resulting case backlogs frequently mean that justice delayed is justice denied. In addition, judicial ineptitude, neglect, and corruption fuel a pervasive lack of confidence and discourage reliance on the formal justice sector.

4.3 INSTITUTIONAL DEFECTS

As Beetham articulates, “although elections form a key mechanism for the popular control of government, they are of limited effectiveness on their own without institutions that secure a government’s continuous accountability to the public.”¹⁹⁵ For Gutto, “elected representatives can play a democratic role only to the extent that enabling institutions of governance with clear systems and procedures that are secured by a normative framework and laws exist.”¹⁹⁶

Institutions are necessary to support individual freedoms. This is regardless of the value of freedom prevalent in any society.¹⁹⁷ Institutions employed in a democracy could be both formal and informal. By formal institutions I mean the executive, legislature and the judiciary. These institutions’ specific roles and functions can be best understood and implemented when articulated in a constitution or equivalent rule of law. Informal institutions are those other institutions put in place to support and help the working of formal institutions. There is an increasing awareness of the importance of institutions for democracy and development. Political, economic and social institutions, both formal and informal, interact with each other to shape the distribution of wealth and power in a given society. This can be done through formal and informal means. Informal means include sanctions, taboos, customs, traditions, and codes of conduct and formal means are constitutions, laws, and property rights. Most new democracies possess all the formal institutions of democracy, these institutions often remain empty shells, failing to function effectively and provide the necessary checks and balances. Institutionalising checks and balances creates a democratic polity which will naturally contribute to the emergence of self restraining state. Horizontal accountability requires the prevalence of the rule of law and entails the existence of agencies of restraint and accountability and independent institutions legally and politically empowered to restrict the powers of the executive.

¹⁹⁵ David Beetham, “**Democracy and Human Rights: Contrast and Convergence,**” Seminar on the Interdependence between Democracy and Human Rights, Organized by the United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, (Geneva: 25-26 November 2002).

¹⁹⁶ Gutto Shadrack, “**Current Concepts, Core Principles, Dimensions, Processes and Institutions of Democracy and the Inter-Relationship between Democracy and Modern Human Rights.**” Seminar on the Interdependence between Democracy and Human Rights. Organised by the United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights. (Geneva: 25-26 November 2002).

¹⁹⁷ Thomas D. Jeitschko et al., “**Economic Security and Freedom: Why Some Democracies Survive and Others Fail**” 2008 p. 9 Electronic copy available at: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1325304>

Chief among the informal institutions in any democracy is the electoral commission. The existence of an independent electoral body however called is a *sine qua non* in any democratic contestation.¹⁹⁸ The primary objective of any electoral administration body is to deliver free and fair election services to the electorate. In doing this, it must ensure that the integrity of every electoral process is adequately safeguarded from incompetent officers and fraudulent manipulators. Failure in this regard will not only adversely affect the quality of service delivered but may also jeopardize the public perception of the competence and impartiality of the electoral administration. Except for a few dotted exceptions, elections in most new democracies are generally badly organized especially by the incumbents.

Electoral institutions must aim at efficiency. In most emerging democracies, with Nigeria as a case study, there is a great degree of vulnerability to allegations of undue influence and bias, thereby making the entire process more susceptible to credible judgment, which inevitably leads to a limited acceptance of election results and of the whole process. The aftermath of 2007 general election witnessed a plethora of election petitions which resulted in a number of them being overturned in favour of the initial losers. While this may be seen as a feature of a developing judiciary, it is not practically so as a lot of these decisions were reached after years ranging from one to three and sometimes even four. The implication of this is that loser has the luxury of holding an electoral office for a period longer than necessary. It would seem then that as far as elections are concerned in emerging democracies, those who rig to win have some gains too.

Electoral institutions must be robed with a garb of integrity. Usually, incumbents in emerging democracies face their challengers by taking control of the state apparatus, especially the electoral institution so that they can further consolidate their power.

Institutions provide the rules of the game; they define the procedures that govern human social, economic, and political behaviour. When principles of human rights and the rule of law are undermined, this will inevitably affect the related institutions. Institutional administrators must ensure that in all its operations due regard is paid to the rule of law. The capture of democratic institutions by the powerful in our societies and around the world, the huge concentration of money and very often the huge concentration of the media in the hands of a few, have made most fledgling democratic institutions vulnerable.¹⁹⁹

The institutional capacity of the state is in most cases determined by the efficiency of the government. This depends, to a large extent, on the combination of the rule of law and democracy. The rule of law not only demands effective and efficient institutions but also a democratic environment within which these institutions have to function.

¹⁹⁸ Jadesola Akande, "***The Legal Framework and Institutional Mechanisms For Free and Fair Elections: Challenge For Nigeria***" paper presented at the 2nd Fellows' Lecture of the Nigerian Institute of Advance Legal Studies (Lagos, 2007), p.27.

¹⁹⁹ Larry Diamond, "***Universal Democracy?***", Hoover institution Publication Policy Review No: 119 June 1st 2003. See <http://repositories.cdlib.org/csd/03-05/>

Political parties form a pivotal institution in a healthy democracy. Conventional wisdom has made it unthinkable that democracy can operate without them. They aggregate and represent interests. They recruit political leaders and disseminate political information. They socialise citizens into democratic politics. Without well-functioning parties, governments and legislatures have little chance of representing wider society in a meaningful way. Parties are the bridge between government and society, both in the ways they translate society's demands into political ideas and programmes, and in the way they hold government to account on society's behalf.²⁰⁰ They must also be able to live up to its promises as it is one of the institutions that must work for any emerging democracy to fully implement the rule of law. In most new democracies, political parties suffer from a lack of credibility and trust. They are also frequently beset with persistent problems of self-interest, corruption, ideological incoherence, and narrow electoralism. This leads to shallow political participation outside elections and further weakens governmental accountability. In the long run, the result is a sense of collective public frustration about what democracy can deliver.

Political institutions more generally have seen a loss of public trust in most emerging democracies. Parties have been called the weakest link in the democratic process. While this does not mean there is less support for democracy, in either the old or the newer democracies it is, undoubtedly, a cause for concern. Many parties in most emerging democracies, especially in Africa are more distinctive in ethnic, religious or regional terms than in ideological ones. Their supporters also tow the same line. There is a large divide between party elites and society, between leaders and party members or supporters. It seems that in Africa that the people, first and foremost, want to see the rule of law established and some improvement in their basic living standards by comparison the idea of competitive party politics is less important, most probably, alien.²⁰¹ This expectation is similar in most emerging democracies, more as, political parties are frequently poorly institutionalized, with limited membership, weak policy capacity and shifting bases of support. They often rely on narrow personal, regional or ethnic ties, rather than reflecting society as a whole; they are typically organizationally thin and insufficiently funded, coming to life only at election time; they seldom have coherent ideologies or policy agendas; and they are frequently unable to ensure disciplined collective action in parliament. As a result, parties often struggle to manage social conflicts and fail to deliver public goods or to promote development.²⁰²

Carothers admitting the weakness in new or struggling democracies analyses thus;

- *Parties are corrupt, self-interested organizations dominated by power hungry elites who only pursue their own interests or those of their rich financial backers, not those of ordinary citizens.*

²⁰⁰ Peter Burnell, ***Building Better Democracies: Why Political Parties Matter*** Westminster Foundation for Democracy Report (London 2004), p. 1.

²⁰¹ Ibid p.11

²⁰² Benjamin Reilly, Per Nordlund and Edward Newman, ***Political Parties in Conflict Prone Societies: Encouraging Inclusive Politics and Democratic Development*** United Nations University Press Policy Brief number 2, (Japan 2008), p.2.

In Nigeria, for instance, except for the ruling People's Democratic Party and a handful of others, the bulk of the 63 registered parties appear to be in existence only during elections.

- *Parties do not stand for anything; there are no real differences among them. Their ideologies are symbolic at best and their platforms vague or insubstantial.*
- *Parties waste too much time and energy squabbling with each other over petty issues for the sake of meaningless political advantages rather than trying to solve the country's problems in a constructive, cooperative way.*
- *Parties only become active at election time when they come looking for your vote; the rest of the time you never hear from them.*
- *Parties are ill-prepared for governing the country and do a bad job of it when they do manage to take power or gain places in the national legislature.²⁰³*

The failure of the rule of law in new democracies can thus be easily traced to the shortcomings in electoral competition that are characteristic of imperfect democratic governments.

Parties need funding in order to survive, compete, and perform their democratic functions, both during and between election campaigns. Yet, political money and those who donate it are widely seen as problematic and in most emerging democracies and as threats to democracy. It is important that the risk of corruption and political finance abuses must be taken seriously, too, particularly where institutions are weak as in most emerging democracies. True, parties with insufficient resources cannot build popular participation, however parties with excessive resources may drive out competitors while becoming isolated from their own social bases.²⁰⁴ It could also result in poor governance and further undermine the rule of law. Thus, political parties' funding must be encouraged, monitored, controlled and in certain cases prohibited.²⁰⁵ Without these measures a single party, or at most a small number of factions among the wealthy and well-organized segments of society, would likely emerge as the dominant party(ies). This seems to be the exact situation in Nigeria and most fledgling democracies.

Institutions also help to check political insecurity among political office holders who has the tendency to stop at nothing in order to ensure that they remain in power, possibly for as long as they want to. The main potential checks on these temptations can be by political institutions that force governments to internalize the social costs of their opportunistic behaviour. For example, institutions of political representation make governments responsive and accountable to broader constituencies through competitive elections, and often restrain governments' discretionary authority by creating multiple players whose approval is required for policy changes. Institutions, where interests are rightly placed and people conscious, can moderate conflict, aggregate demands into public policy backed by a working consensus, and so earn legitimacy.

A central concern in many new democracies is the weak commitment of the governing institutions to reducing poverty, and the inability of the poorest members of society to apply the pressure necessary to make it a higher priority. Any reformative agenda would aim not merely

²⁰³ Thomas Carothers, ***Confronting the Weakest Link: Aiding Political Parties in New Democracies*** Washington, DC: Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, (2006), p.4.

²⁰⁴ Michael Johnston, ***Political Finance Policy, Parties, and Democratic Development*** in John Gould (ed.) ***Political Parties and Democracy In Theoretical And Practical Perspectives*** National Democratic Institute for International Affairs Journal (Washington 2005), pp.3-5.

²⁰⁵ See Chapter 5

at building institutions and rules that are not just efficient but also fair, and that are developed through a democratic process in which all people have a real political voice.

Existent institutions must also watchfully guard against electoral fraud. Electoral fraud deprives any new democracy of the ability of establishing legitimacy and credibility is vital to it. The amount and severity of the fraud depends on the ability of government, the international community, and other social institutions (political parties, independent media, civil rights advocates, monitoring organizations, etc.) to effectively protect the freedoms and rights of voters and candidates.²⁰⁶ The media has been acclaimed as an effective instrument in playing the roles of leadership, watchdog, electioneering and accountability/ whistle blowing.²⁰⁷ A fearless and effective watchdog is critical in fledgling democracies where institutions are weak and pummelled by political pressure. Where electoral fraud is left to fester, electoral apathy and civic irresponsibility is the resultant effect.²⁰⁸

4 SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS

There is an emerging consensus that structural factors such as social, and cultural conditions and legacies impact on democratic consolidation. Democratic consolidation requires the evolution of a democratic political culture where all the main political players view and accept democracy as the only acceptable option. The building of such a culture will take a long term commitment. This is the main challenge emerging democracies are facing today. In any democracy, the ability to enjoy freedom depends not only upon the current state of political rights formally granted, but also upon attitudes in society towards people expressing and agitating for their beliefs; beliefs which may or may not be widely shared. Citizens must also have the capabilities to assert rights even in their ordinary interactions with employers, spouses, and neighbours. Benefits of democracy may be fully enjoyed only in societies that have consistently placed a high value on individual freedoms.²⁰⁹ This may in addition to courts and other legal institutions require material wellbeing, a certain level of education, freedom from hunger and fear.

There are many cultural factors that affect the establishment and implementation of human rights in emerging democracies. In many new democracies legal reforms were brought in from the outside, and have thus remained at a superficial level, without affecting the daily lives of the ordinary people. For these people, human rights issues are only a topic for discussion at the institutional level at most. For instance, while equality is the principle upon which rule of law is based, in many societies inequality is rife, with certain sectors of society living lives of great oppression and poverty such as women, children and the disabled. Women's roles as mothers

²⁰⁶ Rafael López-Pintor, *“Assessing Electoral Fraud in New Democracies: A Basic Conceptual Framework”*, IFES Electoral Fraud White Paper Series USA 2010, p.6.©2010

²⁰⁷ Osakue Stevenson Omoera, *“The Import of the Media in an Emerging Democracy: An Evaluation of the Nigerian Situation”* 22 J Soc Sci., pp. 33-38 (2010) www.krepublishers.com

²⁰⁸ Kunle Ajayi, *“Electoral Administration in Nigeria and the Challenges of the 2007 Elections”* 2 The Soc. Sci., 146 (2007)

²⁰⁹ Thomas D. Jeitschko et al., *Op. Cit.*

and bearers of children, or as bearers of a collective identity, often render women as targets of specific policies and practices.²¹⁰ The lives of millions of women in Pakistan are circumscribed by traditions that enforce extreme seclusion and submission to men, many of whom impose their control over women with violence. For the most part, women bear the traditional male control over every aspect of their bodies, speech and behaviour with stoicism, as part of their fate. In cases where a woman is believed to have 'dishonoured' her family by having a male friend, marrying a man of her choice or seeking a divorce, tribal councils-in some parts of the country known as jirgas- may decide that all those responsible be killed or otherwise punished. In its view, this restores the woman's 'honour'. Jirga law is rooted in tribal customs and in the power of elders.

Sometimes cultural change happens with economic development, increasing education, and exposure to the global environment. West African elites are yet to ground their democracy into their cultural idiosyncrasies and thoughts and mint a "West African way" that is drawn from the soul of the region.

Most young democracies that are developing or emerging are faced with typical problems, such as poverty, poor health services, inadequate education, or internal conflict. Where any of these exists, the appreciations of what rights exist are largely unknown. Incidentally, these factors abound in most emerging democracies. Flowing from this is also the inability of most emergent democracies to satisfy the economic aspirations and yearnings of the people.

Cultural diversity can also constitute an obstacle to stable democracy. Countries must learn how to manage diversity through federalist arrangements to devolve power, assimilation of immigrants, and complex mixes of laws and customs designed to include, not exclude, those from different cultures. The problem arises when one ethnic or religious group seeks hegemony over others, or when some minorities perceive that they are being permanently and completely excluded from power, including any meaningful control of their own affairs. Identifying, then implementing, the kinds of policies and institutional arrangements by which minorities can be protected and all citizens can feel they have a stake and say in the political system helps secure stable democracy.

Corruption involves the abuse of entrusted power for private gain. It could also represent non-compliance with the "arm's-length" principle, under which no personal or family relationship should play any role in economic decision making, be it by private economic agents or by government officials. Corruption in any society engenders mismanagement of resources, which could likely result in under development, poverty and chaos in the polity.²¹¹ Corruption flourishes in areas where the profit from corruption is high and the risk of detection low, where

²¹⁰ Rashida Manjoo, ***"The South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission— a Model for Gender Justice?"*** Prepared for the United Nations Research Institute for Social Development (UNRISD) Report on Gender Equality. Switzerland, 2004 p. 3.

²¹¹ Yinusa A. Muhammed & Basil O. Akanle, ***"Democracy under the Shadow of Corruption in Nigeria: A Reflection of some Issues and Way Forward"*** 3 The Soc. Sci., 299 (2008)

temptation coexists with permissiveness. Where institutional checks on power are missing, where decision-making remains obscure, where civil society is thin on the ground, where great inequalities in the distribution of wealth condemn people to live in poverty, where there is too much regulation of public administration. It is also possible that corruption is alive and well even where political, economic, legal and social institutions are well entrenched. The more endemic the problem of corruption, the more likely it is to be accompanied by other serious deficiencies in the rule of law such as abuse of power and human rights abuses. Corruption subverts democratic institution. Where a country is riddled with widespread corruption and nepotism, fundamental democratic institutions such as judicial systems, legislatures, political parties, even the presidency fail to function adequately and lack legitimacy. Consequently, there will be a resultant public distrust in government institutions and political leaders.²¹² It is easy to claim that neither democracy nor the rule of law has any enemy worse than corruption. Left untreated, we know that corruption undermines the integrity of governments by negating the rule of law and democratic institutions, distorting the allocation of public and private resources, damaging the environment, robbing citizens of their rights and making the public administration unreliable. While it is harmful in the established democracies, it is even more so in newly emerging ones.

Another social factor that undermines the effectiveness of the rule of law in emerging democracies is the influence of the international community. No matter how debatable the latter may be, the truth remains that unless emerging democracies focus on how best human rights can impact positively on the rule of law in their particular states, only very little will be achieved in that regard. Meeting the challenges in prospective, new and emerging democracies requires a concerted and sustained commitment from the international community. More often than not, this 'concerted and sustained' commitment cannot be provided for by the international community either because they do not have the requisite commitment or that they are in a hurry to move on to the next country where they envisage possible rule of law or human rights violations. The citizens of the new democracies are the ones who will bring clarity and definition to their society. No outsider can build democracy for citizens of emerging democracies. Emphasizing this, the UN Deputy Secretary-General, Asha-Rose Migiro referred to Africans as the main determinants of what their future entails.²¹³ Citizens of emerging states where rights and the rule of law are undermined must make demands on themselves that recognize that democracy, while expanding human well being and progress, is essentially subversive of existing conventional social and political orders and relations. Usually this demand entails struggles and hard toil. This process includes reconstructing artificial states, that is, States that do not enjoy the basic characteristics of a state. External support plays only a secondary role in helping to provide them with the greater capacity and means their development process requires. According to Thomas Carothers, "democracy assistance is

²¹² Carlos Santiso, *Op. Cit.* 157.

²¹³ Asha-Rose Migiro, "**Continental Integration of Africa as a Prerequisite for Political, Social and Economic Development**", Remarks at the United Nations Conference on Continental Integration Italy, 2010.

something like additional petrol in the tank which allows the car to go further and faster, but it's not the driver or the steering mechanism".²¹⁴ On the other hand, one may admit that the experience in Kenyan 2008 elections shows the importance of helping emerging democracies to do more than mimic election management techniques. Human rights need to be embedded in practice and in law so that winning partisan or ethnic majorities do not suppress minority losers.

An additional feature that hampers human rights in emerging democracies is hostility and violence. In almost of the world's emerging democracies, democratization seems to be characterized by violence. This has tended to put the democratisation process on the line in many of these states, threatening the prospects of democratic stability and consolidation. Most recent examples include disputed and violent elections in Kenya and Zimbabwe, where the attendant search for redress through official and unofficial responses has, altogether, been largely trapped in deepening contradictions. Violence in these state ranges from ethnic, electoral and the likes. While violence on the whole has the ability to manifestly deny or deprive persons who live in such communities or states their basic rights, electoral violence further deprives citizens their right to enjoy democratic rights. Electoral crises can either be on election day or further escalates onto the future. Election day violence includes the snatching of ballot papers or boxes, assaults on opposition agents or parties, and harassment or intimidation by security agents. In the aftermath of an election, electoral violence may take the form of violent protests against electoral rigging, whether real or imagined, and of the state's deploying its apparatus of force in response to the protest, thereby further fuelling the violence.²¹⁵ Elections provide people with an opportunity to express other grievances. Electoral violence may be thus caused by political contestation, resource-sharing, social justice, ethnic rivalry and marginalization, religious differences or other real or perceived malaise. In the 123rd Assembly of United Nation's Inter-Parliamentary Union and Related Meetings, William Madzimbire, a Rapporteur noted that the challenge facing countries that have denied their people democratic space to express themselves is the prospect of political and armed conflicts.²¹⁶

Civil society, sometimes referred to as "democratic society," creates opportunities for active citizenship and direct involvement in the functioning of a democracy. Civil society is an

²¹⁴ Thomas Carothers, *"Democracy Assistance Without a Plan"*, Carnegie Endowment for International Peace Publication (Washington, 2009) www.carnegieendowment.org

²¹⁵ Nigeria's April 16th 2011 presidential election was followed by violence in the northern part of the country. A good number of youths doing their mandatory one year service were killed. Their offence is that they were used as ad-hoc electoral staff. They were accused of supporting President Goodluck Jonathan, who is from the southern part of the country, to victory.

The Human Rights Watch puts the figure of lives lost at 800. The election which is acclaimed on of the freest in the Country's history is also the bloodiest. See the Punch Newspaper, Tuesday, 17 May 2011. www.punchng.com

²¹⁶ Draft Report on *"Providing a Sound Legislative Framework Aimed at Preventing Electoral Violence, Improving Election Monitoring and Ensuring the Smooth Transition of Power"* (Geneva, 2010).

More than 1,000 people lost their lives and an estimated 300,000 were displaced from their homes in the violence that followed the December 2007 elections in Kenya. See Human Rights Watch, *"2010 World Report"* (USA, 2010) p.128

intermediary entity standing between the private sphere and the state. It provides a voice for popular will. Thus, it is safe to posit that a weak civil society has also the danger of undermining the workability of human rights in any society. The danger is more apparent in any emerging democracy. In most new democracies, while credit must be given to civil societies for ensuring transition to democracy, what they lack is the ability to sustain it. In the wake of the “third wave” of democratisation, non-governmental organizations were seen as critical agents of change. The initial enthusiasm towards civil society appears to be receding. In Africa, for instance, they have tended to assume by default core functions of the state in the areas of health care and education, which is often too weak to assume its responsibilities or has collapsed altogether. In many more emerging democracies civic organizations lack full knowledge of democratic principles and human rights standards and as such do not know what they are supposed to protect or ensure its availability and practicability.

Without a vibrant and activist civil society, the effectiveness and impact of institutions and accountability process would nevertheless be diminished.²¹⁷ The key elements of civil society include an independent media, human rights groups, professional associations, religious institutions, pro-democracy groups, labour unions, sources of policy expertise independent of the state, and associations that may include organizations dedicated to social services, development, health, education, human rights, women’s empowerment, or other issues. Many governments see increasing capacity of the nongovernmental sector as a threat, and continue to support restrictions on the media and civil society. The Nigerian civil society organizations can be described as being hamstrung by the all-powerful state, segmented and urban biased, with a low degree of social embeddedness. It is not uncommon to discover civil society groups that rely on the respective government where they play host for funds to run their organization. The poor economic conditions of most emergent democracies has also led to the emergence of civil society that are state-inclined because members of such groups believe strongly that by showing loyalty to the incumbent government, material resources is assured. The effect of this is that, their policies are largely dictated by the government.

An active civil society has the additional benefit of fostering respect for the rights of other citizens by creating environments of diversity and dialogue. It goes to say, therefore, that where there is no freedom of information, there is bound to be restricted knowledge. Freedom of information, in that sense, implies a form of empowerment or better still, it signifies freedom from ignorance, from servitude and ultimately freedom to choose. An informed person is empowered person. In Nigeria, the Freedom of Information (FOI) Bill was only recently passed into law by the legislature. As at the time of this write up, the bill is still awaiting assent by the President.

Illiteracy is another major factor that hinders effective human rights appreciation in most emerging democracy. The benefit of education cannot be over-emphasized. Education allows citizens to be more sensitive to the democratic spirit and be

²¹⁷ Gutto Shadrack, “**Current Concepts, Core Principles, Dimensions, Processes and Institutions of Democracy and the Inter-Relationship between Democracy and Modern Human Rights.**” Malaysian Journal on Human rights Vol.3, No1 June Malaysian Human Rights Commission P. 11 2009.

better skilled for participation in democratic processes in institutions. It is a means of resistance to undemocratic forces. Lack of it hinders the appreciation of Economic, Cultural and Social rights thus making it easy for most government to avoid their justiciability.

If democracy and good governance go together, then positive effects must connect democratic contestation with governance quality. Democracy can create the conditions for effective rule of law when its protectors and strongest advocates in most case, the voters—are in a position to observe how politicians behave and choose to replace them if they fail to deliver. Where they do not possess this power or it has been striped off them, it will also be mean that they have been striped of the right to negotiate proper implementation of human rights in the state.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

The global trends toward democratization paint a promising picture of the world. However, sound institutions and democratic governance do not develop overnight. With good governance increasingly being acknowledged as one of the key factors in encouraging growth, it is important that all policy makers remain focused on the basic elements that constitute accountable and responsive governance. For many emerging democracies in Sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America and elsewhere, the biggest challenge is to institutionalize the newly chosen multiparty democracy systems and to help democracy deliver in terms of reducing poverty and improving the quality of life. Presently, political transitions in Africa are being caricatured to subvert the genuine and widespread aspiration for democratic governance.²¹⁸ Yet knowing our human rights is essential in today's world. The rule of law can only operate where there is clear commitment by leaders to operate within the law in both public and private interests. In addition, it would seem that the weaker the democratic values of a state, the quicker or easier it is likely to plunge into violent conflict. In such situation, the states not only threaten their own populations but also risk destabilizing neighboring democratizing countries.

While Democracy is said to be the only form of political regime compatible with respecting all categories of rights, particularly these five—economic, social, political, civil and cultural,²¹⁹ this does not establish electoral democracy automatically or promote the enforcement of rights in any democratic nation. Several policy interventions are required to realize a range of rights under democratic government. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) identified four defining features of a democracy that are based on human rights:

- *Holding free and fair elections contributes to fulfillment of the right to political participation.*
- *Allowing free and independent media contributes to fulfillment of the right to freedom of expression, thought and conscience.*
- *Separating powers among branches of government helps protect citizens from abuses of their civil and political rights.*
- *Encouraging an open civil society contributes to fulfillment of the right to peaceful assembly and association.²²⁰*

Democracy, as noted earlier, is not homogeneous. Developing a framework of institutions that fit a country's structure and circumstances requires measures that celebrate diversity. Happily,

²¹⁸ John W. Forje, ***Political Renewal: Democratic Governance, Political Parties And Interests Groups – Emerging Issues – Unfolding Odysseys*** Paper Delivered At The 27th African Association For Public Administration And Management(AAPAM) Annual Roundtable Conference, Held At Zambezi Sun Hotel, Livingstone, Zambia,(December 2005) p.8.

²¹⁹ UNDP Human Development Report 2000 P. 56. Democracy, I believe, also makes respecting all other emerging or developing categories of rights not merely possible but easier.

²²⁰ UNDP Human Development Report 2000 p. 56.

nations no longer face the choice between authoritarianism and democracy. The challenge for the present century is to deepen and enrich fragile democracies. Egypt's nascent democracy is beginning to take its first steps along a difficult road toward genuine democratic governance after long reigning President Hosni Mubarak was forced out of office by the citizens.

However, commitments must be matched by performance and as had earlier been stated, protecting democracy requires vigilance.²²¹ Threats to democracy have not ceased to exist. A good number of young democracies have not managed to improve the living conditions of much of the population, and the expectations that many had conferred on democracy have been disappointed. As we have seen time and again, the transition to democracy is delicate and difficult and can suffer severe setbacks. These setbacks do not disappear when democracies are entrenched in nations. There is a critical need to strengthen the human and institutional capacity of these institutions, and to improve their operational effectiveness. Encouragement has always been given (and must continue to be given) to support fledgling democracies. The United Nations for instance, assists Member States by supporting emerging democracies with legal, technical and financial assistance and advice. For example, the United Nations has given concrete support for elections in more and more countries, often at decisive moments in their history – more than 20 in the last year alone, including Afghanistan, Palestine, Iraq and Burundi.²²²

Third world civil society has gone from an intermediary entity standing between the private sphere and the state, as earlier asserted, to being co-opted by the state, more like partners, in advancing their selfish interest. This is mainly due to lack of funds. The lack of mutual set goals and exchanged information which has risen due to the politicization of civil society has rendered it so weak to hold state officials accountable.

The most harmful notions about democracies that have spread in recent years are the clichés that democracy is a system characterized by “one person, one vote” and “majority rule.” Such notions suggest that the largest social group, whether defined by religion, ethnicity, or class has the right to run a society as it sees fit. This formula is a recipe for factionalism. Democracy demands much more. In some established democracies, such as the United States, an effort to balance democracy is achieved by establishing multiple organs of government with different bases of representation. New democracies are increasingly directed their electoral systems to achieve similar results. Nigeria, for example, requires political parties to include representatives of two-thirds of the country's states on their executive councils and forbids those parties from using communal or regional references in their names, mottos, and emblems. Indonesia has taken this logic a step further, requiring that political parties establish offices in two-thirds of the provinces nationwide and recruit a significant number of members in two-thirds of the

²²¹ See Chapter 2

²²² United Nations *“Toward Development, Security and Human Rights for All”* Larger Freedom Report See www.un.org/largerfreedom/chap4.htm

districts and municipalities within these provinces in order to compete in parliamentary elections.²²³

Naturally, governments are more likely to respect and promote the particularly democratic aspects of the rule of law when they are more exposed to democratic pressures. This is despite the minor opposite that exist to this opinion.²²⁴

Parties by themselves do not preclude people seeking power through arms, bribery, the power of a charismatic leader, or the strength of the mob, and parties themselves are open to a range of abuses. But without them, citizens and societies have few genuinely democratic alternatives.²²⁵ For democracy to be meaningful citizens must have some real choices between alternative sets of both people and policies. If parties do not exist to structure choices and run the government, some other organizations would have to fulfill that role. If the political choices presented to citizens were merely a scattering of individuals not organized in groups, it is hard to imagine how a government made up of such non associated individuals would function coherently.²²⁶

In addition there are many weak or failed states, with fragmented national identities and prone to violent conflict. Conditions in these countries, many of them in Africa, not only threaten their own populations but also risk destabilizing neighboring democratizing countries. Nigeria's twelve years of democracy has not established a clear link between elected official and the electorate. Elected officials owe their positions more to political godfathers, violence and thuggery, bribery, electoral fraud and manipulation than the preferences of the electorate. There is therefore no incentive for them to perform once in office or fulfill any promises made.²²⁷

There is a need to enlighten citizens, community and party leaders alike, to understand that for democracy to flourish the marketplace of ideas must also be seen to flourish. Collective pursuit and strengthening of democratization and opposition to unconstitutional changes of Government is a good step in the right direction. Ensuring better protection of human rights is, therefore, critical to conflict prevention, mitigation and resolution. Democracies can only flourish if they are rooted in the fertile soil of civic society in which human rights are respected. An active civil community must also show trust for one another room for interacting as political equals.

²²³ J.A. Goldstone & J. Ulfelder, *"How to Construct Stable Democracies"*, the Washington Quarterly (2004-05) © 2004 by The Center for Strategic and International Studies and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. pp.17-18.

²²⁴ In Libya, Col Ghadafi instead of heeding his country's call to relinquish power took to publicly killing demonstrators.

²²⁵ Micheal Johnston *"Political Parties and Democracy in Theoretical and Practical Perspectives: Political Finance Policy, Parties, and Democratic Development"* The National Democratic Institute for International Affairs Journal (Washington, 2005) p.5

²²⁶ Thomas Carothers, *"Confronting the Weakest Link: Aiding Political Parties in New Democracies"* Washington, DC: Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2006 p.10.

²²⁷ Nair Ahmed El- Rufai, *"Nigerian Democracy and Prospects For the 2011 Elections (2)"* © Nigerian Pilot Daily Newspaper www.nigerianpilot.com

Recent happenings in the world, particularly with the growing democratic waves, shows that world belong to democracy at all levels of governance.

RECOMMENDATION

The maintenance of an independent and accountable judiciary is fundamental to ensuring accountability for human rights violations, where they occur, the rule of law, constitutionalism and the protection of human rights and the constitution. An independent judiciary is the pillar in a system of checks and balances against arbitrary power. Judicial independence is recognized in many international and regional human rights instruments as constituting one of the cornerstones of the rule of law and good governance. It involves two principles;

- (a) That judicial power must exist as a power separate from and independent of, executive and legislative power, and
- (b) Judicial power must repose in the judiciary as a separate organ of government, composed of persons different from, and independent of those who compose the executive and legislature.²²⁸

Review of governmental acts by an independent body in the interests of maintaining the efficacy of the constitutional guarantee of individual rights is an essential and important mechanism of good and democratic governance. Additionally, such a review by individuals assures the individual's personal participation in government. Judicial independence also involves institutional and financial autonomy. Judicial appointments, training and the court system have to curb executive authority – not succumb to it. Judges and magistrates must recognize that they are duty bound to provide society with the highest possible standards of service and commitment and that a failure to maintain this is rightly a matter of public concern. Upholding the judicial oath of office to administer justice to all persons should be the primary aim of all judicial personnel. Direct recourse of people's organizations to the judicial system, through public interest litigation,²²⁹ also helps protect rights and should be encouraged. Every society must support and protect the judiciary for judges remain an easy target for those wishing to make partisan political capital. The Cairo Declaration urged governments to guarantee the financial independence of judiciaries.

The society also expects judges to accept fair and temperate criticism of judgments and to maintain appropriate standards of ethical behavior. Legitimate criticism of judges arising from the discharge of their duties, even if somewhat emphatic and unhappily expressed, is permissible as being the exercise of the freedom of expression. However, unjustified and

¹¹. Muna Ndulo, ***“Rule of Law Programs; Judicial reform, Development and Post Conflict Societies”*** ANLEP Working Paper No. 2(September 2009) pp.15-17. Also available at: www.sum.uio.no/research/network/anlep

²²⁹ Nigeria's Fundamental Rights Enforcement Procedure Rules of 2009 incorporated Public Interest litigation to it.

unreasonable attacks on judiciary, undermines the judiciary's constitutional role. A transparent and independent removal procedure is also essential. The matter should not be left in the hands of the executive as it then provides a potential weapon through which to intimidate judges and thus help create or maintain a pliant judiciary. In effect, it undermines the separation of powers and the independence of the judiciary.

As has been noted earlier, another matter which impacts the independence of the judiciary is the funding of the judiciary. Sufficient funding to enable the judiciary to perform its functions to the highest standards should be provided. Appropriate salaries, supporting staff, resources and equipment are essential to the proper functioning of the judiciary. As a matter of principle, judicial salaries and benefits should be set in a transparent manner. The salaries and benefits should be secured by law. The administration of monies allocated to the judiciary should be under the control of the judiciary. Financial autonomy is fundamental. Without it, the executive can seriously impact judicial independence by limiting the judiciary's access to the funds voted to it by parliament and/or by assuming control of the services and staff upon which the judiciary depends. For judges and magistrates to efficiently and effectively discharge their duties without undermining the confidence of the people, they must be drawn from a wide array of different backgrounds to ensure a better understanding of the experiences of those with whom they will be dealing. The lawyer whether as a judge, legislator, member of the executive or as a private legal practitioner has the corresponding duty to let leaders know that they are not above the laws of the land and that government is a call to duty.²³⁰ Where a country has multi-ethnic groups, judicial appointment should cut across these ethnic groups so as to eliminate or minimize the risk of any group being repressed or marginalized.

Furthermore, it is necessary that emerging democracies, where it is notice that there is backlog of cases in court, should take appropriate measures to see that cases in court are expeditiously dealt with. The major way in which this can be achieved is by appointing more judges and building more court room. Where the situation of allowing backlog of cases are left to fester, the saying, 'justice delayed is justice denied' will not be truer. Inordinate delay of cases amounts to abuse of the right to obtain justice. It also allows perpetrators of all forms of human rights abuses and injustices to persist knowing that they may never be brought to justice.

Efforts to reform the police must be taken as serious business. There are two dimensions to police reform. The police have to be protected from arbitrary orders from the political system. And the people have to be protected from rights abuses inflicted by the police. This requires monitoring of police actions and other measures to promote human rights norms in the police force. There is need to strengthen the investigatory capacity of the Police Service Commission by providing adequate funding, staff, and training to enable the Department of Discipline to independently investigate complaints of police corruption and other serious abuses.²³¹ The

²³⁰ Okpara Okpara et.al., **"Human Rights Law and Practice in Nigeria"** Vol. 1 (Chenglo Limited Enugu, 2005)p.388

²³¹ Human Rights Watch **"Everyone's in on the Game: Corruption and Human Rights Abuses by the Nigeria Police Force"**(New York, 2010) Copyright © 2010 Human Rights Watch p. 9.

government should implement without delay the core recommendations of the 2008 Presidential Committee on the Reform of the Nigeria Police Force and prioritize measures addressing financial transparency and oversight, public complaint mechanisms, and monitoring and discipline of police personnel. Ensure that sufficient resources are allocated to enable effective implementation of these recommendations.²³²

Minority participation in decision-making structures should be promoted by giving minorities' special weight in legislative procedures and by having opposition and minority representatives chair parliamentary committees. Forums for young persons to share governance idea and prepare them for such roles should be provided. In Nigeria, there appears to be a gulf between her leaders and the younger population, while it remains socially conservative, the younger generation is influenced by other cultures.²³³ This does not only show in fashion and language but extends to political and other socio-cultural ideas. Re-engaging young people with national political issues may take time, but could develop in them an appetite not just to ask questions but actually to challenge the clique of a relatively few 'Godfather' who still dominate Nigerian political life.²³⁴ Young people's participation in governance issues will surely breathe new life into the presently stagnant life that most new democracies process whereby they mostly depend or await international assistance to shake the stagnancy in their polity.

The sanctity of the vote must be guarded by autonomous election commissions, international monitors and, if necessary, interim regimes for the sole purpose of transferring power from one elected regime to another. The new practice developed by the Nigerian's Independent National Electoral Commission whereby results after each election are laudable. It ensures transparency of the Commission.²³⁵ There are still a number of obstacles that need to be overcome if the Commission is to achieve the much touted fairness and equity by the time that the entire exercise is concluded. These include the prevention rather than the detection of blatant acts of wanton hijacking of materials and intimidation of voters as has been recorded in a number of states, a special task force of security agents whose main task is prevention, rather than intervention after the act, must be effectively deployed to polling stations on election days.

²³²2008 Presidential Committee on Police Reform, "**Main Report**", p. 49. The report defined new guidelines for the appointment, removal, and tenure of the inspector general of police to insulate the police from political manipulation. It further advised the Nigerian government to reform the budgetary process and financial oversight of the police create a credible public complaint mechanism and prosecute abusive police officers. The committee also recommended that the police leadership overhaul the anti-corruption XSquad, create effective monitoring mechanisms, and establish functioning forensic laboratories.

²³³ Current President Jonathan's campaign has been noted for its use of Facebook to deliver his message to Nigeria's younger electorate and expatriate communities. Much as the country belongs to 'Facebook generation' this currently applies to only a small percentage of the population.

²³⁴ Sola Tayo, "**Key Issues In Nigeria's 2011 Elections**" Programme paper for Chatham House (London,2011) p.4

²³⁵ This practice introduced in the April 2011 polls saw notable political 'godfathers' losing in their own polling booths. Former President Olusegun Obasanjo and his Daughter, Iyabo, a serving senator lost in their polling centre at the African Church Grammar School, Ita Iyalode in Abeokuta. The Obasanjos had used the power of incumbency to consolidate their political leverage in Ogun State in the 2003 and 2007 election, but may have now lost out due to exposure to a free and fair electoral setting. See www.vanguardngr.com

An independent and impartially administered electoral process is a prerequisite for the conduct of free and fair elections in any country. Where elections are generally free and fair, election petitions are generally reduced.²³⁶ In established democracies, however, national and local government officials handle election administration. It is, therefore, imperative for emerging democracies to establish and promote independent and impartial election management bodies to manage the electoral process effectively so as to ensure that violence-free and peaceful elections pave the way for the smooth transfer of power.²³⁷ While it may be impossible to organise an entirely clean election due to human and technical errors, flaws must not alter or predetermine the outcome. Similar to the judiciary, poor funding undermines the independence, capacity and autonomy of any electoral body. Nigeria's nascent democracy is gradually losing its lustre and vibrancy due to the tilting to plutocracy and institutional disfiguration, impelled by uncompromising politicians. Electoral offenders must be punished without fear or favour.²³⁸ In most cases funds are either not released or where it is released for the conduct of any electoral process it is released late. There is also the need to modify the manner in which appointment of electoral officers is done.

Political parties must be internally democratic. Party leaders should be elected and replaced through open, competitive processes. Political parties should adopt codes of conduct for internal democracy and for tolerant behaviour during the electoral process. One major aspect that must be regulated to preserve enforcement of the rule of law in emerging democracies in a manner that would ensure adequate safeguard of human rights is that of political party financing. Though money is required to finance democracy, undisclosed and unregulated campaign funding has the potential to warp the political contest and the governing process that follows an election. In its November 2003 Technical Publication Series, the Office of Democracy and Governance in the United States Agency for International Development proposed six main approaches to controlling money in politics. They are setting contribution limits, contribution bans on certain bodies, fixing spending limits for all purposes, setting campaign time limits, public disclosure of donations and imposing limits of public financing. It is possible for combination of these approaches to be included in a given reform initiative, but there is no agreed upon formula for what constitutes the best mixture of approaches.²³⁹ Contribution limits are usually higher for corporate or other organizations than for individual donors. Public disclosure effectively enforced is the backbone of most approaches to controlling money in

²³⁶ The just concluded National Assembly elections in Nigeria saw incumbent losers such as The Speaker of the Lower Legislative House congratulating his victorious opponent, rather than the erstwhile practice of protesting results and not conceding defeat under any circumstance.

²³⁷ Mr. Jesudasu Seelam, "**Providing A Sound Legislative Framework Aimed At Preventing Electoral Violence, Improving Election Monitoring And Ensuring The Smooth Transition Of Power**" Draft report presented at the 123rd Assembly Of The Inter-Parliamentary Union And Related Meetings Held at Geneva, on 4 - 6.10.2010

²³⁸ In the National Assembly 2011 Poll, The Commissioner for Education in Ogun State, Nigeria, Yemi Akinwonmi and six others were on Monday 11th April 2011 remanded in prison custody till April 27 a Chief Magistrate Court for alleged electoral offences. What is unclear is whether the alleged offenders belong to the opposition party or faction of the ruling People Democratic Party.

²³⁹ Office of Democracy and Governance, "**Money in Politics Handbook: A Guide to Increasing Transparency in Emerging Democracies**" U.S. Agency for International Development, Technical Publication Series (Washington 2003) p.2.

politics. Enforcement of public disclosure can be strengthened indirectly by working with coalitions to lobby for better enforcement of laws and regulations, to assist in monitoring disclosure reports, and to encourage the will of enforcers to follow through on their responsibilities. Enforcement may also be strengthened through improving the legal framework, addressing legal barriers to effective public disclosure and/or the institutional weakness of enforcement bodies.²⁴⁰ More importantly, the use of public resources by incumbents for campaign purposes must be criminalised.

Perhaps it would be foolhardy to expect much from the parties when they seem to be a myriad of inadequacies in the internal running of these parties. In Nigeria, the party primaries that was held prior to the 2011 polls witnessed a number of criticisms. The general reference to 'consensus candidacy' appears to refer to situations where candidates representing such parties were not democratically chosen but were merely chosen from the will of the party leaders.²⁴¹ To talk about internal party democracy is also to refer to the extent to which a party subscribes to and abides by the basic and universal democratic tenets. This includes the extent to which a political party has put in place and follows mechanisms that allow for the party executive to be responsive and accountable to its membership. It also means that in such a party, there is internal political contestation or competition and participation of the members in the affairs of the party.²⁴² If parties are building blocks of democracy, they cannot afford not to be democratic themselves for to do is a contradiction both in terms and in values. To this end Government should encourage political parties to strive towards creating or improving intra-party democracy for effective management of party affairs. For instance, gender equality ought to be enhanced and selection of leaders and election candidates be more democratized.²⁴³

Governments should create the political space, and encourage partnerships, for monitoring and promoting human rights. Ultimately, governments and the people benefit when the media are open and civil society institutions free. It enhances conditions conducive to partnerships for creating norms and accountability for human rights. Capacity-building and training of civil society activists and leaders should focus on advocacy, networking, policy-making and lobbying, civic education, the role of the media and work with the press. Relevant legislation should be developed to facilitate civil society initiatives. A strong civil society can enhance the social and political influence of otherwise underrepresented groups (such as the poor), increasing their effectiveness in influencing governance institutions and making the latter more responsive to their needs.

An independent, investigative media creates higher expectations regarding transparency and disclosure of potential conflicts of interest. It makes the media an effective and credible

²⁴⁰ Ibid.p.4.

²⁴¹ The Action Congress of Nigeria was widely criticized for this.

²⁴² The People's Democratic Party Post 2011 election Crisis in Ogun State Nigeria borne out of the rift between former President Olusegun Obasanjo (a Political Godfather) and Governor Gbenga Daniels (Obasanjo's one-time political godson) carefully illustrates this. The result is that the party in the state was broken into several factors over personal loyalties not ideologies.

²⁴³ John W. Forje, "**op. cit.**" p.26.

watchdog, helps to accustom officials to an inquisitive press and build a culture of openness and disclosure that has made democratically elected governments more accountable. To be independent and viable on their own, newspapers need to diminish their dependence on subsidies of any kind especially from the government. In cases where wealthy businesspeople subsidize the media, they end up making them mouthpieces for their interests. News organizations must work toward financial viability so they can buy their independence. The media should keep citizens engaged in the business of governance by informing, educating and mobilizing the public. They need to have the requisite skills for the kind of textured and in-depth reporting that new democracies require.

In many fledgling democracies, the media become the target of reprisal from powerful groups and individuals who benefit from the silence of a muzzled press. At least six journalists were reportedly killed in Somaliland in year 2009, some targeted for assassination and others killed by the stray gunfire that has claimed so many civilian lives.²⁴⁴ Journalists also need to be protected by laws that guarantee their rights. In many new democracies, old laws dating back from the authoritarian past impose harsh punishments for libel, restrict access to official information and impose strict licensing requirements for media companies. The repeal of such laws and the enactment of more media transparent laws are necessary for better appreciation of human rights. In Nigeria the Freedom of Information (FOI) Bill has recently been assented to by President Goodluck Jonathan.²⁴⁵ While the passage of the Bill has been lauded by as the clearest demonstration of the power of civil society working together to influence public policy and initiate reform, however there are still criticisms that it has been watered down by the Nigerian legislative houses.

Pro-poor human development policies and a reasonable distribution of the resources from economic growth are vital companions to legal and institutional advances in human rights. People must be free from the oppression of tyranny, from torture, from discrimination, from the fear of leaders who will imprison or make them “disappear”. But they also must be free from the oppression of want -- want of food, want of health, want of education, and want of equality in law and in fact.²⁴⁶ The process of economic policy-making has to respect rights of participation and expression. And the content of pro-poor economic policies has to be aimed at increasing resources and targeting programmes to the vulnerable. Where there is less education, there is likely to be less voters’ awareness. This means that in that such society, the people will be ignorant of the power of their votes.

Unless the people are educated and use their votes intelligently, democracy can never prosper and run smoothly. Democracy is a function of education. It cannot be managed effectively and justly without sound education of the voters and their high level of information. All

²⁴⁴ See Human Rights Watch, **“2010 World Report”** p.160

²⁴⁵ The Bill was signed into Law by the President on 30th May 2011 after a long wait. The FOI Bill was first submitted to the 4th National Assembly in 1999 when the country returned to democracy.

²⁴⁶ Hillary Clinton, **Speech on “the Human Rights Agenda for the 21st Century”** delivered 14 December 2009, Georgetown University, Washington, D.C.

democracies, particularly new democracies, will only evolve, develop and flourish with an informed, engaged citizenry. Democracy education is needed to provide party supporters with sound opportunities to acquire knowledge, skills, attitudes and democratic values that enable them to exercise citizenship and foster their capacity to participate effectively and responsibly in their societies. Civic education should be instituted to enlighten citizens about their rights and obligations in a democracy. To achieve this government can incorporate democracy education in the school curriculum at all levels. This education should include teaching on political tolerance.²⁴⁷ Institutions of higher learning in fledgling democracies should provide the forum for educating party members. This will enable members acquire essential knowledge to protect, sustain and advance the democratic gains made in the transition process and also revitalize the commitment to building and nurturing a democratic culture and good governance. In addition, information communication technologies are instruments in facilitating democracy education.

The system of government or its mechanism must provide for an independent, fair, expeditious and accessible dispute settlement mechanism to address electoral disputes during the election cycle or after the election results. A system whereby electoral disputes are still in court half way into the constitutional term of office of the disputed winner, more so whereby the extant structure does not provide for refund of gains that the office provides the a loser who is thought to have won, would albeit encourage electoral fraud and violence.

There must be measures aimed at strengthening of the role of the opposition, facilitating constructive dialogue and the dissemination of information between stakeholders and building public trust and confidence in the electoral system.²⁴⁸ For there to be efficient democratization and better enforcement of the human rights and the rule of law, citizens must imbibe positive values as well as any other attribute and be willing to tolerate the expression of a plurality of political opinions, including those different to their own. The best public policy should arise out of competition among divergent views and ideas that are expressed in a free and transparent public discourse.

Many countries have well-drafted laws on the books that are widely ignored especially by leaders who try to perpetuate themselves in their office. The recent happenings in Egypt, Tunisia and Libya should teach them that the patience of citizenry who have them for leaders are growing thinner by the day, more so, the end is always a bitter one.²⁴⁹ They should also understand that what is important is the quality of service rendered, not the number of years of service.

²⁴⁷ S. T. Akindede et. al., ***“Political Intolerance As A Clog In The Wheel Of Democratic Governance: The Way Forward”*** African Journal of Political Science and International Relations Vol. 3 (8) September, 2009 p. 375 © 2009 Academic Journals

²⁴⁸ Sandra Day O’Connor ***“The Importance of Judicial Independence”*** in Leslie High et. al.(eds.) ***“Constitutionalism and Emerging Democracies”*** Issues of Democracy, IIP Electronic Journals,Vol.,No.1, March 2004 p.28.

²⁴⁹ After more than four months’ standoff, defiant Cote d’Ivoire self-declared president, Laurent Gbagbo who refused to give up power after his rival, Alassane Ouattara, was named the winner of last year’s presidential election has been detained. See www.guardiannewngr.com

External democracy supporters will continue to face strategic dilemma except it is ordered in a manner that shows it is not a mere power tussle. They must understand that isn't sufficient to introduce democratic principles and set up effective institutions. Democracy can first consolidate when a pluralistic political culture can sustainably support the emancipation of disadvantaged groups, the democratic solution to conflicts, and differences of opinions and ideas.²⁵⁰ They must also seek to allow the citizens of any particular country to be at the fore front of any democratic entrenchment and consolidation.

The triangle formed by the concepts of rule of law, human rights and democracy is not an equilateral one; circumstances may often require that greater emphasis be placed on one element, without detaching it from the others. Thus, a State whose institutions have broken down may need to re-establish democratic institutions and the rule of law to ensure respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. Countries that have already suffered a return to military government—or fear the resurgence of authoritarian forces—might well consider the utility of a truth and reconciliation commission to create an environment conducive to democracy and respect for human rights.²⁵¹ Truth commissions are generally understood to be "bodies set up to investigate a past history of violations of human rights in a particular country - which can include violations by the military or other government forces or armed opposition forces."²⁵²

All forms of corruption, particularly political and economic corruption, undermine democratic values and institutions, degrade the enjoyment of rights, and impair the ability of the State to implement human rights. Resources to combat corruption should be made available readily and widely at both the national and international levels. The law must clearly and effectively prohibit bribery and misuse of public funds. It must forbid conflicts of interest and require public officials to make their personal and family finances transparent. The salary level of civil servants should be competitive and ensure reasonable living standards for a household.

New democracies must generate a more open market economic reform in which it is possible to accumulate wealth through honest effort and initiative in the private sector with the state playing a limited role. The wider the scope of state controls over economic life, the greater the possibility of graft by abusive and predatory elites. Reducing administrative barriers to doing business and implementing corporate-responsibility initiatives can address the supply side of the corruption problem. Strong guarantees of property rights, including the ability of owners of small farms and informal-sector workers to obtain titles to their land and business property, can

²⁵⁰ Marc Saxer, *"New Approach to Democracy Support"* FES Briefing Paper 16, Department for Development Policy (Germany, Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung Publications 2009)p. 6.

²⁵¹ In South Africa, its Truth and Reconciliation committee was used to address the hurt of the Black Majority. In Nigeria, the Human Rights Violations Investigation Commission was given mandate to investigate cases of human rights abuses committed since the first military coup in 1966 and make appropriate recommendations to the government . The Commission has long completed its work and its report submitted. However this report was never officially released to the public. States in Nigeria such as Rivers and only recently, Osun has also established their own truth Commissions.

²⁵² Priscilla B. Hayner, *"Fifteen Truth Commissions -- 1974 to 1994: A Comparative Study."* In Human Rights Quarterly, Volume: 16 Issue: 4. 1994, p. 558.

provide the foundation for a broader institutional landscape that limits government corruption.²⁵³

The international community's fight against corruption should be broad and holistic in nature, taking full account of political corruption in a more serious way, with a view to consolidating emerging and restored democracies. The enactment of appropriate legislation should be prioritized to address the various structural weaknesses that allow corruption to thrive. Also, International cooperation is essential to counter corruption. States must, for instance, provide for their banking system to ensure that the profits of corruption cannot be retained, but are returned to the State of origin. Anti-corruption strategies should be nationally led and based on the principles of transparency and accountability. The right of access to information, including government information, and freedom of expression and the press should be respected and enhanced. Working towards the realization of the Millennium Development Goals provides an important opportunity to confront underdevelopment and corruption.²⁵⁴

No regime should be called a democracy unless its rulers govern democratically. If freely elected executives (no matter what the magnitude of their majority) infringe the constitution, violate the rights of individuals and minorities, impinge upon the legitimate functions of the legislature, and thus fail to rule within the bounds of a state of law, their regimes are not democracies.²⁵⁵ Human rights are most vulnerable when the exercise of power is not rule based. An elected leader must face institutional curbs to restrict arbitrary action.

Emerging democracies must demonstrate that they can solve governance problems and meet citizens' expectations for freedom, justice, a better life, and a fairer society. Democratic governance and respect for human rights are crucial to the goal of integrating Africa into the global economy. Recent history has taught us that democratic governments that safeguard political and economic freedoms foster more effectively the conditions for sustainable economic growth. True many new democracies are struggling because of the burdens they inherited however effort must be made by all involved to take the issue of rights and rule of law seriously.

It is not enough for civil society actors to forge a common cause among themselves, across their otherwise diverse interests. They must also link up with sympathetic (or even opportunistic) forces in the state and the party system. This is because institutional reforms are ultimately enacted by parliament or by some special constitutional reform process that in most countries parliament must consent to.²⁵⁶ While political parties are often perceived negatively by the

²⁵³ Larry Diamond, **"Democracy in Retreat"** essay adapted from his book, **"The Spirit of Democracy: The Struggle to Build Free Societies throughout the World"** (Times Books, 2008), © Larry Diamond

²⁵⁴ The situation in Nigeria at present is a far cry from the expectations of the Millennium Development Goals. Few years to the actualizations of set goals, it seems Nigeria which is a signatory to the goals have done very little to ensure that they are actualized.

²⁵⁵ Juan J. Linz & Alfred Stepan, **"Toward Consolidated Democracies"** Journal of Democracy 7.2 US: John Hopkins University Press 1996 p.15

²⁵⁶ Larry Diamond, **"What Civil Society Can Do To Reform, Deepen, And Improve Democracy"** Paper presented to the Workshop on **"Civil Society, Social Capital, and Civic Engagement in Japan and**

population, see civil societies as a problematic group, a healthy and balanced relationship between civil society and political parties is essential for democratic governance.

National Human Rights Commissions should be established in all emerging democracies. While its presence may be taken for granted in established democracies, it is not so for new democracies. Government must also ensure that the Commission, when established must be allowed to act as independently as possible. They should in no way be subjected to the dictates of the government. In Nigeria, the Commission's leadership was dissolved by the government before the end of its mandate. Thankfully with the new National Human Rights Commission bill signed into law, it secures the independence and funding of the NHRC.²⁵⁷

Efforts must be made to strengthen the political will of citizens of new democracies that are found in want of it. The strict enforcement of all the above discussed recommendations will surely improve the political will of persons in all nascent democracies.

Cultural diversity has two sided implication. While its impact can be positive, it can also have negative implications. Where differences in culture are discovered to negatively impact emerging democracies, a conscious effort particularly by the government of the day should be made to mitigate these impacts. The Government of the day must avoid polarizing itself along cultural lines as it has the tendency to make other cultural groups to want to exert their superiority in whatever way it can; peaceful or not. The citizens must be allowed to choose their identity and lead their lives without being excluded from other choices such as educational and employment opportunities. Government should also develop multicultural policies to address cultural exclusion. They should also understand that democracies have the tendency to propel cultural consciousness because of its freedom of idea and purpose.²⁵⁸ States must find ways of forging national unity amid this diversity. Fledgling democracies will remain so except they understand that growth will remain stunted unless people respect diversity and build unity through common bonds of humanity. Cultural differences must also be recognized in the laws and institutions of the state. Citizens likewise have a corresponding duty to ensure that their manner in which they exhibit their cultural affiliations is aimed at strengthening the general application of rights and the rule of law in new democracies. While there are chances they may know how to go about it, they must keep peace as they watch word.

Citizens of new democracies expect to be granted social as well as political rights. If democracies do not more effectively contain crime and corruption, generate economic growth, relieve economic inequality, and secure freedom, the rule of law and the people's rights, people will eventually lose faith and turn to authoritarian alternatives. The realization of human rights in emerging democracies will continue to be undermined as long as the right attitude as

the United States." Sponsored by the Japan Foundation Center for Global Partnership, The Asia Foundation, and the program on U.S. Japan Relations at Harvard University, June 12-13, 2001, Tokyo. See www.stanford.edu

²⁵⁷ Amnesty International Press release, 29 March 2011. See www.hrea.com

²⁵⁸ United Nations Development Programme, **"Overview: Human Development Report 2004: Cultural Diversity in Today's World"**, Human Development Report 2004, pp. 1-12 see www.hdr.undp.org

explained above are not formed. To achieve this also means that new democracies must learn to discipline their priorities.²⁵⁹

Finally, I would prescribe a certain amount of prayer.

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²⁵⁹ Chidi A. Odinkalu, “*Back To The Future: The Imperative of Prioritizing For The Protection Of Human Rights in Africa*” (Cambridge University Press: 2003) J.A.L. Vol. 47, No. 1 p.37 ©School of Oriental Studies

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